

Sweden's Fair Share in the Context of Limiting Global Average Temperature Increase to 1.5°C

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Author Biography

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Dr. Holz studied at the University of Leipzig and the University of Glasgow, and her degrees include an M.Phil. from the Department of Sociology and a Ph.D. from the School of Social and Political Sciences, both at the University of Glasgow. She completed post-doctoral research in the School of Political Studies at the University of Ottawa, and in the Department of Geography and Environmental Studies at Carleton University in Ottawa. Dr. Holz has been teaching in higher education at undergraduate and graduate levels for over 20 years, most recently with appointments at the School of Political Studies at the University of Ottawa, and at Carleton University in the Department of Geography and Environmental Studies and the Norman Paterson School of International Affairs.

Request from Aurora: Request for quantification of Sweden’s fair share

This request is made in the context of systemic, human rights-based climate litigation against the Swedish state. The legal argumentation underlying the choices made in this request is available in the summons application.

Scholarly literature provides different ways of quantifying states’ share of global efforts pertaining to addressing climate change, which result in a range of different estimates for how large Sweden’s share is. However, determining what constitutes a *fair* contribution according to national, European and international law is a legal question, not a scientific one, and therefore the range is constrained by Aurora’s interpretation of the law.

For the present report, we request to operationalise the legal obligation for states to contribute with their fair share of global mitigation measures required to limit warming to 1.5 °C, and apply this operationalisation to Sweden. Sweden’s legal commitments mean that a fair share should be determined in line with the legal principles of equity, common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities, harm prevention, precaution, highest possible ambition, cooperation, intergenerational equity, sustainable development and the polluter pays principle as well as the 1.5 °C temperature limitation objective and in accordance with the best available science. This legal framework is the basis for these instructions.

The requested report should:

- I. Describe the theoretical background to different approaches to quantifying states’ fair shares according to the relevant body of academic literature,
- II. Review literature on methodologies for quantifying states’ fair shares and select to focus on studies that
 - i. articulate approaches for sharing the remaining global carbon budget or the global mitigation effort required to limit global warming to 1.5 °C,
 - ii. quantify such shares among nation states,
 - iii. apply allocation approaches whose equitability is justified by the study in a way that is not contrary to the legal principles outlined above, and
 - iv. together form an inclusive representation of the broader available literature.
- III. Quantify,¹ through applying the methodologies from the selected literature, Sweden’s fair share of
 - i. the remaining global carbon budget for keeping global warming below 1.5 °C with 67 and 83 percent probability² and
 - ii. the global effort required to limit global warming in 2100 to 1.5 °C with no or limited overshoot, with 67 and 83 percent probability.³
- IV. Categorise the quantified approaches into three categories, based on Aurora’s understanding of the compliance with the legal principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities:
 - A. Approaches that factor in states’ differentiated responsibilities (defined as historical contributions to cumulative greenhouse gas emissions since 1990 or earlier)⁴ and respective capabilities.
 - B. Approaches that factor in responsibility **or** capability, but not both.
 - C. Approaches that factor in **neither** responsibility nor capability.

To facilitate comparisons between Sweden’s fair share and its mitigation measures, the present report should, where applicable, provide results for fair share allocations for total territorial emissions for the period until 2045⁵ including the same greenhouse gases included in Sweden’s mitigation targets, as an aggregate for the sectors industry, product usage, agriculture, fossil energy and waste.

¹ Allocations should be made no later than 2016, after the Paris Agreement was adopted in December 2015. United Nations, *Treaty Series*, vol. 3156, p. 79. This also means that, where applicable, Sweden’s emissions that have been in excess of its fair share effort allocation since 2016, i.e. its fair share shortfall, should be compensated for by correspondingly more stringent mitigation measures in the near future.

² As described by IPCC. (2021). Summary for Policymakers. In: *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896, table SPM 2, and updated by Forster, P. M., et al. (2025). Indicators of Global Climate Change 2024: Annual update of key indicators of the state of the climate system and human influence. *Earth System Science Data*, 17(6), 2641–2680. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-2641-2025>, p. 2663.

³ I.e. those of the “C1” pathways summarized in the IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report that have the same probabilities, or higher, of limiting warming to 1.5 °C as the remaining global carbon budgets described above. IPCC. (2022). Summary for Policymakers. In: *Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change, Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, doi.org/10.1017/9781009157926, box SPM.1 & table SPM.2.

⁴ This is the year of the first IPCC report (IPCC & WMO (Eds.). (1992). *Climate change: The 1990 and 1992 IPCC assessments, IPCC first assessment report overview and policymaker summaries and 1992 IPPC supplement*), the start of UNFCCC negotiations (UNGA (1990). *Protection of global climate for present and future generations of mankind*. UN Doc. A/44/207, para 10), and a reference year for emissions reductions under the UNFCCC (art. 4.2(b)) and EU and Swedish domestic mitigation targets (Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 (‘European Climate Law’), article 4.1; & prop. 2016/17:145, s. 25 & 29).

⁵ The year of Sweden’s domestic net zero target. Prop. 2016/17:145, s. 25.

Executive Summary

Limiting global warming to 1.5°C, the scientifically based consensus target under international law, requires ambitious global mitigation. For the world to collectively implement this mitigation, it is central to determine how much each country should contribute and it is widely understood that these contributions should reflect each country's "fair share." How countries have agreed to share this mitigation between them is a normative question informed by law. Nevertheless, countries' fair shares cannot be effectively quantified without physical science identifying the total global mitigation required and without operationalizing the legal obligation of equitable mitigation sharing.

Aurora's request for this report describes the legal basis for this fair share obligation. Based on this, the report is requested to quantify Sweden's fair share of the global mitigation effort that, according to the best available science, is required to limit warming to 1.5°C,* using allocation approaches from the available scientific literature. The report reviews this literature and discusses the most salient approaches to allocate global mitigation efforts or carbon budgets to countries based on several ethical principles, before quantifying Sweden's shares according to several of such allocation approaches.

According to Aurora's request, a key aspect of the definition of "fair shares" is the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities. This means that allocations should only be considered "fair shares" (Category A approaches according to Aurora's taxonomy) if they are based on the ethical principle of responsibility (allocating larger shares of the mitigation effort to states with higher contributions to cumulative GHG emissions) as well as the principle of capability (allocating larger shares to states with higher economic and social capacity).

The results show that under all assessed fair share allocation approaches that are consistent with Aurora's request, there is a very significant gap between Sweden's fair share and Sweden's current mitigation measures.

It is notable that even allocation approaches that take account only of responsibility or capability but not both (category B) show a significant gap between Sweden's allocation and its current mitigation measures. Even according to certain approaches that cannot reasonably be considered fair (as they take account of neither responsibility nor capability – category C), Sweden's remaining carbon budget is, at best, minuscule: for example, when dividing the presently remaining global carbon budget equally among countries according to population ("equal per capita allocation"), Sweden's share corresponds to less than two years of its CO₂ emissions at present levels. **Thus, even approaches that do not constitute a fair share in accordance with Aurora's request typically show that Sweden's emissions are exceeding its allocation, often by far** (categories B and C).

There are two general approaches for determining a country's fair share with regards to global mitigation based on a given underlying principle. The first is to divide the global remaining carbon budget, resulting in a national remaining carbon budget. Such budget-sharing approaches show that Sweden has already more than exhausted its fair remaining carbon budget and has overdrawn it by 1,630 to 4,590 MtCO₂ for

* As per Aurora's request for this report, mitigation consistent with limiting warming to 1.5°C with at least 67% or 83% probability (respectively) is considered.

category A approaches (for comparison, Sweden emitted about 39 MtCO₂ in 2024). **Regardless of fair share budget allocation approach, Sweden does not have any remaining entitlement to the global remaining carbon budget for limiting global warming to 1.5 °C and has also accrued a substantial carbon debt** (category A, but also B). This remains true even for allocation approaches that ignore some, but not all, of the fundamental equity principles.

The other method is to allocate the global emissions pathway, resulting in national emissions pathways. For fair share allocation approaches that are consistent with Aurora's request, Sweden's fair share of global 1.5 °C-consistent mitigation is an equivalent of an emissions reduction of 145 % to 162 % below 1990 levels in 2030, and 262 % to 291 % below 1990 levels in 2045. When adjusting for the shortfall between Sweden's actual emissions compared to its fair share since the adoption of the Paris Agreement, these **fair share allocation approaches for emissions pathways show that Sweden's emissions should be 154 % to 173 % below 1990 levels in 2030, and 270 % to 302 % below 1990 levels in 2045.**

Taken together, the results present a range of possible sizes of Sweden's fair share depending on specific normative assumptions. For each level of ambition from this range, it is crucial to consider what that ambition level means for the global mitigation and for the mitigation required in all other countries. Specifically, if all countries would simply choose the approach that is most lenient for them, global mitigation would be insufficient, and the temperature limit would be exceeded.

Since all fair share allocation approaches considered here result in a negative remaining carbon budget (an overdraft) or emissions reductions far in excess of 100 %, respectively, **mitigation efforts consistent with these fair shares cannot simply be implemented in Sweden's territory alone – and instead imply mitigation cooperation (including through finance) with other countries on a very substantial scale**, because the difference between Sweden's mitigation fair share and the most ambitious domestic mitigation has to be implemented in other countries with Sweden being responsible for ensuring that this mitigation takes place, including by providing finance and other means of cooperation and support.

1. Introduction

In the context of identifying a suitable global response to mitigating climate change, the question of how to share the necessary effort among actors arises. Given that countries, in the decision adopting the Paris Agreement and elsewhere since, have agreed that each should make contributions to this collective effort that are “fair and ambitious” (UNFCCC 2015, para. 28), this report is specifically concerned with, and focused on, the question of sharing this effort *fairly* (as opposed to: in some other way).

Given also that the Paris Agreement clarifies the UNFCCC’s objective to “prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system” in a way that allows “ecosystems to adapt naturally...” (UNFCCC 1992, Art. 2) to mean, inter alia, the objective of “pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C”¹ (UNFCCC 2015, Art. 2), this report is concerned more specifically with the question of fairly sharing a global effort that can achieve this temperature threshold. This question draws equally on normative considerations informed by domains such as political science and moral philosophy as well as on the physical science of climate change. The former inform the approach to equitable sharing of effort and the latter determines the total size of the effort to be shared. This report considers three different ways for conceptualizing this effort, thus combining different lines of evidence from physical science: First, by considering fair sharing of an amount of carbon dioxide emissions that can be emitted to ensure that the temperature threshold will not be breached, often called “carbon budgets” (explained in more detail in section 3.2 with results in section 4.1). Second, by considering fairly sharing the global emissions under modelled emissions pathways consistent with that temperature threshold (with details in section 3.3.3 and results in 4.2.1). Third, by considering fairly sharing the global mitigation effort to deviate from emissions trends to achieve global emissions under modelled emissions pathways consistent with the temperature threshold (sections 3.3.4 and 4.2.2).

A thorough treatment of the physical science base of climate change is beyond the scope of this report, as is a thorough analysis and discussion of the relevant international law provisions as related to fair effort sharing. Instead, the report takes as a starting position the Request provided by Aurora (reproduced above), and in this context considers the applicable interpretation of the Paris Agreement’s temperature limitation objective to refer to a carbon dioxide budget for 1.5°C, or an emissions pathway that achieves 1.5°C or lower by 2100, both with probabilities of 67% and 83%. Additionally, the Request provides for an interpretation of the relevant equity principles of the UNFCCC, the Paris Agreement and other applicable provisions of international law, to mean that fairness in sharing the collective mitigation effort must at a minimum include due considerations of both capability and responsibility. Therefore, while, for completeness, both literature review and the quantification of effort sharing approaches also include discussion of approaches that do not meet these criteria, the emphasis of the quantified results is on those approaches that meet the criteria.

1 The full text of the relevant provision of Article 2 of the Paris Agreement is “Holding the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.” It is now widely recognized that this phrase does not refer to two separate objectives, but instead articulates two characteristics of a single goal: ensuring a peak of temperature increase “well below 2°C” followed by efforts to reduce warming to 1.5°C.

It is important to establish that it is generally accepted that the question of whether a single country's contribution to a given global effort is *adequate* can only be answered in the context of “fair shares” of this global effort – the IPCC notes that “it is only in relation to such a ‘fair share’ that the adequacy of a state's contribution can be assessed in the context of a global collective action problem” (IPCC 2022: 1468). This report, therefore, is concerned with the question of Sweden's fair share of a globally adequate mitigation effort, to aid in determining what would constitute an adequate effort by Sweden.

As such, the report will first review the literature that addresses the question of fair shares of global mitigation, including a discussion of quantitative approaches for the global mitigation effort and their respective strengths and limitations. The report will then describe the methodology used in this report to select a subset of those approaches for quantification and how these quantifications have been carried out, before presenting the results – for Sweden – of these quantifications and discussing these results.

2. Literature review

Equitable effort sharing has been the topic of discussion in climate negotiations, adjacent discourses, the scholarly literature and in civil society since at least the beginning of the negotiations leading up to, and subsequently under, the UNFCCC and in related discourses (e.g., Agarwal and Narain 1991; Rose 1990; Shue 1992, 1993; UNFCCC 1997; Berk and den Elzen 2001). Important groundwork, that is still relevant today, was laid during this early stage of the discourse, though many of the concepts and proposals developed at the time have largely (e.g., the so-called Brazilian Proposal, UNFCCC 1997) or almost completely (e.g., the formerly influential Contraction and Convergence proposal, Meyer 2004) been set aside. In 2007, the IPCC's Fourth Assessment Report (IPCC 2007) summarized the state of the effort sharing literature at the time by enumerating and summarizing the major specific allocation proposals, which serves as a good overview of the discourse up to that point. A more thorough treatment of the early debates is beyond the scope of the report, though Pelz (2023) provides a helpful sketch of the historical developments.

2.1 IPCC AR5: Four Equity Principles and Their Limitations

Subsequently, The Fifth Assessment Report (IPCC 2014) made two important contributions to the synthesis of the literature. First, in chapter 4, it identified four major equity principles that were “laid out in the UNFCCC” (Fleurbaey et al. 2014: 317) and, for that reason, emphasized in the literature: responsibility, capability, equality and the right to development. Later in the report, the IPCC offered an influential categorization of allocation approaches in the surveyed literature into five categories and linking them to a subset of the equity principles identified earlier, including a catch-all category of “staged approaches” containing approaches based on multiple of the equity principles or, indeed, none at all. This categorization has been utilized extensively in the effort sharing literature subsequently (Pan et al. 2017; Robiou du Pont et al. 2017; van den Berg et al. 2020; Williges et al. 2022), though it has been criticized for excluding important equity principles articulated elsewhere and for including allocation approaches that have no justification in equity principles or that use equity principles that lead to inequitable outcomes when applied to effort sharing in the context of stringent global mitigation (Dooley et al. 2021; Kartha, Athanasiou, et al. 2018).

These critiques will be reviewed shortly, but it is prudent to review the four equity principles identified in chapter 4 of the Fifth Assessment Report in some more detail as they are foundational to the literature's treatment of the problem space. First, Responsibility, as an equity principle in the context of effort sharing, simply holds that the "responsibility for contributing to climate change (via emissions of GHGs) [should be related] to the responsibility for solving the problem" (Fleurbaey et al. 2014: 318). Beyond this general principle, the literature considers a multitude of conceptually and specifically different ways in which this general principle is understood and/or implemented, distinguishing, for example between moral responsibility and causal responsibility, or moral importance of adverse impacts on others resulting (via climate change) from greenhouse emissions. As such, Responsibility, as an equity principle, is also linked to, and often invoked to operationalize, the related Polluter Pays Principle, and is often understood to reflect the UNFCCC phrase "common but differentiated responsibilities" (Rajamani et al. 2021).

Second, Capability or Capacity,² as an equity principle for effort sharing, holds that the contribution an actor makes to solving climate change should be related to the relevant capabilities of the actor. As an equity principle, this is sometimes articulated as reflecting "Ability to Pay," which holds that the higher an actor's ability to pay for preserving or generating a public good (such as: a safer climate) the more they should contribute. While, in practice, this is often operationalized as actors' economic wherewithal, different capabilities, e.g. relating to technological, institutional, or human capacity dimensions may also be taken into account (Fleurbaey et al. 2014). "Capability" as an equity principle is often understood to represent the second component of the UNFCCC phrase "common but differentiated responsibility and respective capabilities" (Rajamani 2016; Rajamani et al. 2021).

Third, Equality, is based on the basic premise that "each human being has equal moral worth and thus should have equal rights" (Fleurbaey et al. 2014: 319), and, as such, it is closely related to egalitarian philosophies. As with the other principles, different specific interpretations exist, including with regards to the question what, specifically, the "equal right" refers to, or, more fundamentally, to the question whether equality, when applied as "equal rights" in the context of effort sharing while disregarding relevant dimensions of inequality between actors, does, in fact, lead to inequitable outcomes, thus violating the very equity principles that is ostensibly represented (Fleurbaey et al. 2014).

Fourth, the Right to Development holds that actors' contributions to solving climate change should consider "that meeting basic needs has clear moral precedence over the need to solve the climate problem" and therefore actors should not be expected to make contributions that would adversely impact their right to development. Right to Development, as an equity principle in the context of effort sharing, is related to, and, indeed, often expressed as "Need," recognizing that the purpose of articulating a positive "Right to Development" is, first and foremost, to assign moral priority to enabling the least advantaged to meet their basic needs and their fundamental right to a dignified life (Dooley et al. 2021).

In the present report, these four equity principles will be utilized to characterize the main ethical justification of specific allocation approaches.

2 "Capability" and "Capacity" are typically used interchangeably in the literature. Chapter 4 of the Working Group 3 contribution to the IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report, for example, uses "Capacity" while Chapter 6 predominantly uses "Capability." (Clarke et al. 2014; Fleurbaey et al. 2014)

As mentioned, chapter 6 of the Working Group 3 contribution to the IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report (AR5), borrowing from Höhne et al. (2014), presents a categorization of allocation approaches in the scholarly literature at the time. The chapter maps its six categories to a subset of the four equity principles from chapter 4, by omitting Right to Development, or Need, as one of the equity principles considered. "Need" is only indirectly operationalized by the "responsibility, capability and need" category of approaches. Since, however, this category is primarily characterized as representing only the "capability" and "responsibility" equity principles, "need" – the equity principle reflecting the moral priority of safeguarding the basic needs of the poorest – is effectively removed from the categorization (Clarke et al. 2014: table 6.5). This categorization has been of substantial influence in the subsequent literature, with studies following this categorization, or a subset thereof, to represent the overall problem space of effort sharing, while subordinating the core equity principle of need (van den Berg et al. 2020; Pan et al. 2017; Robiou du Pont et al. 2016, 2017, 2017; Robiou du Pont and Meinshausen 2018).

At the same time, and often responding to these, the AR5's chapter 6 taxonomy (and its use) has been criticized along three main lines (Dooley et al. 2021; Kartha, Athanasiou, et al. 2018; Teng et al. 2019): that it is, first, an incomplete, and biased, reflection of the discursive space, that it, second, includes, and thereby potentially justifies, allocation approaches that have no relevant justification in equity principles or/and are implemented in ways that are inconsistent with the equity principle they ostensibly represent, and that it, third, is used, via "appeal to IPCC authority" (Dooley et al. 2021: 303) to signal that it represents a comprehensive and complete reflection of the problem space that is somehow endorsed by the IPCC.

First, as Kartha et al. (2018) point out, the IPCC itself recognized, and elaborated elsewhere in the same report, "the relative moral relevance of consumption-based versus production-based emissions, survival versus luxury emissions, progressive versus regressive allocation of mitigation costs, prioritarianism versus egalitarianism and finally – but not least – the right to development and the critical ethical importance of the eradication of poverty" (Kartha, Athanasiou, et al. 2018: 348). Caney (2020) elaborates additional relevant equity considerations. These considerations tend to be ignored in the literature quantifying allocation approaches, and as such, this literature should not be understood or be represented as encapsulating the whole problem space of equitable effort sharing (or, indeed, even the most important fraction of it). In the context of this report, it is worth highlighting that several studies suggest that this systematic bias of the effort-sharing literature generally leads to results that are more favourable to developed compared to developing countries (Dooley et al. 2021; Kartha, Athanasiou, et al. 2018; Teng et al. 2019). As such, it is plausible to assume that studies that would also include these additional dimensions would yield even more demanding results for developed countries like Sweden, compared to studies that do not, like the present report.

Second, the taxonomy from chapter 6 of AR5 has been criticized to give legitimacy to allocation approaches that have no or little justification in the application of ethical principles. Specifically, the inclusion of the "staged approaches" catch-all category, which includes approaches that don't neatly map onto any of the other categories. This includes studies that incorporate different equity principles to differing degrees at different points in time, and/or for different actors (for example, differentiating actors on the basis of their evolving capabilities). Most controversially, it also – implicitly as well as explicitly – includes Grandfathering, an allocation approach that has overwhelmingly been rejected as inequitable in the literature and will be discussed in more detail below. Similar criticism has been raised with regards to some of the approaches included to represent the equity principle of "equality" and operationalize

equality in ways that ignore relevant dimensions of difference and therefore lead to outcomes that should not be considered equitable. Dooley et al. for example, with reference to Aristotle’s *Nicomachean Ethic*, point out that “equality without consideration of unequal needs and vulnerabilities, unequal capacities and unequal responsibility leads to equality for unequals, which philosophers since Aristotle³ have condemned as gross inequity” (Dooley et al. 2021: 304).

Third, making explicit or implicit “appeal to IPCC authority,” studies suggested that by using allocation approaches representing most or all of the categories from AR5 chapter 6, they comprehensively reflect the breadth of the relevant discourse and, indeed, the relevant ethical space. As indicated above, this, of course is an oversimplification, even if just considering the IPCC’s treatment of the matter in the same Fifth Assessment Report (IPCC 2014, e.g., in chapters 3 and 4).

Despite appeals to expand the scope of the treatment of equity in quantitative modelling of emissions pathways (Klinsky and Winkler 2018), mitigation scenarios (Kanitkar et al. 2024), and effort sharing approaches (Dooley et al. 2021), the current state quantitative effort sharing literature is still generally limited to reflecting the four equity principles described in chapter four of the Fifth Assessment Report.⁴ Thus, the limits identified by Kartha et al. (2018) and others regarding additional important ethical dimensions of the effort sharing problem space still apply to the present state of the literature.⁵ In other words, recent work focussed less on expanding the scope of this discursive space and instead on innovating with regards to specific operationalizations interpreting these same principles in various different ways (including, arguably, in ways that contradict the principle that the approach is ostensibly based on). At the same time, important innovations subsequent to the AR5 synthesis of the literature have sought to address some of the main criticisms of it, especially with regards to “staged approaches,” including their treatment of Grandfathering, as well as with regards to specific allocation approaches intended to reflect the equity principle of “equality.” These innovations will now be discussed in turn, after – for context – quickly sketching the main concerns that have been raised in the literature with regards to Grandfathering and certain approaches claiming to reflect the Equality principle.

2.2 Critique of Grandfathering

Grandfathering and approaches based on Equal Per Capita allocations (intended to reflect the equity principle of equality), as mentioned above, require some more attention. In essence, Grandfathering holds that future allocations of emissions should maintain the same proportion of emissions for countries as emissions in the past. In addition to explicit applications, Grandfathering is also used under different names such as “constant emissions ratio” (e.g., Robiou du Pont et al. 2017), “inertia” (e.g., Raupach et al. 2014), or implicitly in work that simply applies the same emissions reduction percentages, relative to fixed historical reference points, to all countries (e.g., Watson et al. 2019). The claim that Grandfathering can be

3 *Nicomachean Ethics* 1131a 23-24 (Aristotle n.d.)

4 Responsibility, Capability, Equality and the Right to Development.

5 In fact, as recently as in the Sixth Assessment Report, the IPCC notes that the every-expanding discussions of equity has not yet found its application in studies that seek to *quantify* equity: “equity issues are often discussed in the literature via frameworks that are well-founded in the ethical literature and that have a strong bearing on effort-sharing, but have not yet been quantitatively modelled and expressed in the form of an emissions allocation quantified framework. These include, for example, ethical perspectives based in human rights [...], human capabilities [...], environmental justice [...], ecological debt [...], transitional justice [...], and planetary boundaries” (IPCC 2022: 472) as well as intergenerational equity and consumption (Dooley et al. 2021).

considered an allocation approach that is based on relevant equity principles has been widely rejected in the literature (Gosseries 2005; Caney 2009, 2012; Kartha, Athanasiou, et al. 2018; Teng et al. 2019; Moellendorf 2020; Meyer and Roser 2010; Dooley et al. 2021; Rajamani et al. 2021; Azar and Johansson 2025).

In fact, even studies that explicitly aim to articulate a defense of grandfathering, in its “moderate” formulation, as a potentially relevant allocation approach, do so on instrumental grounds, after discussing and rejecting claims that it can be justified on grounds of substantive equity (Knight 2013). There are, however, studies that include it nevertheless (e.g., recently, Anderson et al. 2020; van den Berg et al. 2020; Robiou du Pont et al. 2017). The normative claims to include it as based on an “equity principle” are often not provided, or not compelling. For example, van den Berg et al. (van den Berg et al. 2020), in their table 1 list “sovereignty” for grandfathering under the heading “equity principle,” without explaining why this should be considered an equity principle and without engaging with the dominant view in the literature rejecting it. In fact, the texts of the two references provided for justification of using “sovereignty” as an equity principle do not even contain the word.

The most charitable defense of grandfathering as an *ethical* principle, would be based on an argument like the one put forth by Knight (2013), arguing, on instrumental grounds, that if grandfathering is the only plausible path to lead to an international agreement that results in an overall reduction of societal harm, it could be defended on that basis.⁶ Alternatively, taking the claim of “sovereignty” as the justification of grandfathering at face value, it could be argued that the defense of the international law principle of sovereignty has an overriding primacy over considerations of justice, presumably because of the importance of upholding the Westphalian international order that it is based upon. Importantly, neither of these possible defenses include relevant claims relating to equity, and as such, while recognizing that defenses of grandfathering exist, they are not relevant to the question of *equitable* effort sharing.

2.3 Critique of Equal Per Capita Allocation

On the other hand, that equality is an equity principle is, generally, long (Agarwal and Narain 1991) and well established (IPCC 2014). This is based on the premise that each human inherently has the same worth and therefore each human should, in the first instance, be afforded the same rights. However, as

6 Additionally, Anderson et al. (2020) can be seen as an interesting outlier to the two main ways in which literature generally deals with grandfathering, i.e. to either reject it on the basis that it has no defensible justification as an approach embodying equity, or to include it, either without providing any justification or with weak justifications for it embodying equity. They use grandfathering to divide the collective carbon budget of *developed countries only* (as opposed to: all countries) between those countries, after having derived this collective budget with a different approach that more explicitly takes equity into account. They claim that grandfathering is more defensible for apportioning the collective developed-country carbon budget than an apportionment based on equal allocations, as the latter does “not take account of historical emissions, capacity to finance decarbonization, renewable energy resources, the inertia of existing high-carbon and fossil-fuel infrastructure, nor the carbon-intensity of the existing economy” (Anderson et al. 2020: 1295) while the former arguably reflects many of these factors. Unfortunately, they do not provide further justification for this claim. However, since it is intuitively plausible, and given that they use the approach only for allocation among developed countries, which are similar to each other in many relevant aspects (e.g. with regards to their responsibility, capability and stage of economic development), many of the criticisms leveraged against grandfathering and equal-per-capita allocation approaches, when used for allocations among all countries, do not apply. While an interesting assertion and approach, this example is not relevant for the present report that is concerned with effort sharing among all countries, not just developed countries.

mentioned above, specific allocation approaches that seek to implement the equality principle have been criticized on the grounds that they yield results that are not, in fact, equitable. This is specifically true for a class of allocation approaches usually called “Equal Per Capita,” where the amount of permissible emission or emission reductions is allocated to countries proportional to their population, which equal per-capita values for all countries. This, however, ignores the fact that people across different countries (and, indeed, within them) vary greatly, for example, with regards “to the inequalities in people’s needs, their level of development, internal economic stratification and access to other sources of energy” (Dooley et al. 2021: 301) just as it ignores the fact that unequal responsibilities and capabilities have clear moral relevance for considering “equality.” Furthermore, the logic of equal per capita breaks down when intergenerational justice is considered, as acknowledging that future humans have the same inherent worth as present ones and should therefore receive equal shares as well would essentially reduce those per-capita shares to zero (Caney 2020).

As such, it should be held that equality-based allocations (in the sense of “equal per capita”) can only potentially be considered equitable, if they include relevant other dimensions of equity that render the starting point of equality into an outcome of equity. For example, this has been done by adjusting an allocation based on equal per capita for differences in capability (ESABCC 2023; Pelz et al. 2023), or by including notions of responsibility via allocating amounts that are *cumulatively* equal over time (IPCC 2014; ESABCC 2023; Robiou du Pont et al. 2017).

2.4 Innovations since IPCC AR5: “Grandfathering Bias” and Discontinuous Allocations

The AR5 description of “staged approaches” provides that they encompass a diverse group of approaches that use different principles for allocation at different stages (hence the name), with “stage” being understood as either reflecting a progression from one principle to another over time, or as different principles being applied to actors at different stages of, for example, economic development. Importantly, this category also includes grandfathering, as an explicit “stand-alone” approach but also, less explicitly, as an approach that is often used for one or several of the “stages” of other staged approaches. To provide a single example for a larger section of the literature, Kartha et al. point out that in Robiou du Pont et al.’s (2017) implementation of allocation approaches ostensibly based on other principles (equality and capability, respectively), the use of a long “transition period” from a grandfathering-based starting point to allocations based on the other principle results in “nearly half of the remaining carbon budget is grandfathered, rather than being allocated according to the nominal equity principle of each approach” (Kartha, Athanasiou, et al. 2018: 348). Kartha et al. also observed that such transition periods “cannot be rationalized on the basis of avoiding technically implausible reduction rates [when] [...] transferable emissions allocations rather than physical emissions” (Kartha, Athanasiou, et al. 2018: 348) are being considered. This points to the importance of distinguishing between physical emissions and equitable allocations, which will be discussed below in section 2.5.

This observation has also been echoed elsewhere (Robiou Du Pont et al. 2025; Azar and Johansson 2025; CVF 2022; Dooley et al. 2021; Rajamani et al. 2021), where the use of transition periods or, indeed, any allocation approach that starts at present emissions levels is said to show a “grandfathering influence” or “grandfathering effect” which would continue to “reward a lack of action and reduce the implied provision of international support” (Robiou Du Pont et al. 2025: 8).

To address this issue, approaches have been adjusted to begin allocations at a point in the past or by using “discontinuous” allocations that are immediately based on equity. An example for the first approach is the Climate Equity Reference Framework, which, in recent applications holds the allocation start year constant at 2016, the year after the adoption of the Paris Agreement (e.g., Civil Society Equity Review 2025, 2023; Holz 2024a; Holz et al. 2022), whereas examples of the latter include a recent article by Robiou du Pont et al. (2025) or the Climate Vulnerable Forum’s “Paris Traffic Light” Report (CVF 2022).

These innovations have also further reduced the validity of any justification for Grandfathering, even as a starting point, as they demonstrate that “continuous” allocations from present levels are not, in fact, required for allocation approaches as previous literature had assumed. In addition to other studies that add further compelling legal rationale to the rejection of including grandfathered allocations (Rajamani et al. 2021), this suggests that such allocation approaches can no longer be considered equitable in accordance with the present state of the scholarly discourse.

2.5 Physical Emissions and Equitable Allocations

A concept that has long been central to the discourse of equitable allocation for the global mitigation effort, or of emission rights, has been the distinction between actual emissions and equitable allocations, or placing the same concept in a different frame, the distinction between where an emission reduction or removal would take place and who should be thought of being responsible for ensuring that it does. Expressing this point through the lens of mitigation costs, the IPCC notes that “a crucial consideration in the analysis of the aggregate economic costs of mitigation is that the mitigation costs borne in a region can be separated from who pays those costs [...], effort-sharing schemes have the potential to yield a more equitable cost distribution between countries” (IPCC 2014, p. 457, emphasis added).

In essence, this distinction becomes necessary to overcome two related problems. First, the maximum amount that actual emissions in a country can be reduced by is 100% – or the minimum allocation of an allocation of actual gross emissions is zero – even though it is possible that faithful application of an equity principle would suggest higher reductions than 100% or a smaller allocation than zero.⁷ Second, and relatedly, there can be situations where the actual emissions reductions within a country should be larger (or the allocation of emissions smaller) than what equity principles would suggest: the nature of “the relationship between fair shares of mitigation and physical emissions reductions is that, some countries’ share of global capacity and responsibility greatly exceeds their mitigation potential, while the reverse is true for other countries” (Holz et al. 2018: 128). By conceptually distinguishing between actual emissions (or reductions) and equitable allocations, the integrity of the latter can be shielded from constraints due to the limitations of the former.

This distinction allows approaches to determine equitable shares of mitigation to disregard the question of whether these shares would be feasible, or could be achieved at least cost, if implemented within the countries themselves (Rajamani et al. 2021; Höhne et al. 2014; van den Berg et al. 2020; IPCC 2014; Dooley et al. 2021). The IPCC, in the Sixth Assessment Report, recognizes that this essentially requires “extending

⁷ The be clear, emission reductions can be in excess of 100% (or emissions allocations less than zero) if net emissions including removals are considered. The main point here would still apply: that equity-based allocations of mitigation effort can be higher than the maximum net mitigation (including removals) that is physically possible in a given country.

equity frameworks to quantify equitable international support, as the difference between equity-based national emissions scenarios and national domestic emissions scenarios” (IPCC 2022: 476). In other words, by embracing the distinction between actual emissions in a country (the “national domestic emissions,” in the IPCC’s language) and equity-based emissions allocations – with the latter being higher in some countries and lower in others, compared to the former – the question arises how countries can comply with their equity-based allocations if the reductions according to their domestic emissions scenario are not sufficient. Various approaches have been suggested for this, including, chiefly and non-exhaustively, trade of permits (as early as Agarwal and Narain 1991), the provision of climate finance and other support sufficient in scale to cover the shortfall between actual domestic emissions and equity-based allocations (Civil Society Equity Review 2022, 2024, 2015; Holz et al. 2018, 2022; CVF 2022; Fleurbaey et al. 2014), or the use of market-based or cooperative approaches such as under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement (Robiou Du Pont et al. 2025); with each of these approaches having relative advantages and disadvantages. Additionally, countries can implement measures to remove atmospheric carbon dioxide to increase their overall mitigation, though limits with regards to socio-economic, sustainability, and physical considerations have been discussed (Deprez et al. 2024). While a fuller treatment of this issue is beyond the scope of this report, the main insight of these discussions is that equity-based allocation approaches do not need to be constrained by considerations of cost effectiveness or feasibility. Rajamani et al. note that while this “may be a relevant consideration in choosing between alternative means of *implementing* national fair shares, it is not a relevant consideration in *determining* fair shares” (Rajamani et al. 2021: 992).

It is important to note, though, that this distinction clearly has not been consistently applied in the literature defining quantitative allocation approaches, as evidenced by the wide-spread use of transition periods (as discussed above) and the existence of approaches whose design constrains possible results to a maximum of 100% reduction (or allocations of a minimum of zero).

2.6 Characterization of Specific Allocation Approaches

As discussed above, the literature proposes several different quantified allocation approaches that are based on several underlying equity principles, as well as approaches that have been described in theory but not been quantified. A complete enumeration and discussion of all these approaches is beyond the scope of this report, for practical reasons and because many of these approaches are now mostly of historical interest or/and have never received broad attention in the literature. Additionally, as discussed above, allocation approaches have also been implemented that combine grandfathering with other approaches via transition periods, such as per-capita convergence or immediate per capita convergence (van den Berg et al. 2020). Just like grandfathering itself, they are not described here, based on the assessment made above about the legitimacy of their equity claims. However, several approaches are persistently and repeatedly used in the recent literature (as shown for the selection of studies contained in table 1) and therefore warrant further description. In the following, these will be introduced by describing their general principle as well as the variables that typically distinguish specific operationalizations from each other.⁸

⁸ References are not generally for elements of these descriptions as they are very similar across studies. As mentioned, chapter 6 of the IPCC’s Fifth Assessment Report (IPCC 2014) and Pelz et al. (2023) can serve as good overviews, with the latter also covering developments subsequent to AR5.

Responsibility – this concept uses historical greenhouse gas emissions as the main metric through which to determine the allocation of future emissions allowances or shares of the global mitigation effort. Specific approaches generally differ by the time horizon they consider for historical emissions, and by the gases and sectors they include (e.g. including or excluding LULUCF emissions).

Capability – this concept relates the allocation of emissions or of shares of the effort to concepts of capability, with higher-capability countries receiving smaller allocations of emissions or larger shares of the effort. Metrics to measure capability most commonly relate GDP (with variants adjusting, or not, for purchasing power parity) or the Human Development Index. Versions of capability-based allocation approaches include those that make further adjustments for development needs – reflecting the Right to Development principle –, typically by implementing an exemption for the portion of each country’s GDP that is required to meet the basic needs of the population (with variants adjusting, or not, for intra-national inequalities).

Equal Per Capita – this concept assigns emissions or reductions to countries in proportion to their population, yielding equal per-capita figures. As discussed above, unless adjusted to account for relevant dimensions of inequality (e.g. regarding responsibility, capability or need), this approach tends to lead to inequitable outcomes and therefore cannot, under those circumstances, be considered an equitable approach.

Cumulative Equal Per Capita – this concept, based on the principle of equality, ensures that cumulative emissions over time are equal in per-capita terms. Specific approaches differ in terms of the time horizon they consider for calculating the cumulative amounts. Where this time horizon is sufficiently far in the past, this approach can be said to combine elements of responsibility and equality as it effectively adjusts future equal-per-capita allocations for historical over- or underuse.

	IPCC AR4	(Robiou du Pont et al. 2017)	(Pan et al. 2017)	(van den Berg et al. 2020)	(Rajamani et al. 2021)
Responsibility	X		X		X
Capability	X	X	X ^b	X	X
Equal Per Capita	X	X	X	X	X
Cumulative Equal Per Capita	X	X	X	X	X
Responsibility, Capability, Need / GDRs	X	X	X ^b	X	X
Staged Approaches	X		X ^b		X
Others		X ^a	X ^b	X ^c	

^a Grandfathering, or “Constant Emissions Ratio.” While Robiou du Pont classified this as a “staged approach” it is considered “others” here, for comparability with the other studies and because they did not actually implement any stages.

^b “Others” includes grandfathering; “staged” includes “common but differentiated convergence and multi-stage and multi-criteria approaches; “responsibility, capability and need” includes the “South African approach;” “capability” includes an emissions intensity-based approach; “equal per capita” includes the “One billion high emitters” approach.

^c “Others” includes grandfathering and cost-effectiveness.

Table 1: Coverage of most salient allocation approaches in selected studies.

Climate Equity Reference Framework / Greenhouse Development Rights⁹ – this concept combines the equity principles of responsibility, capability and Right to Development (“development need”) by calculating a “responsibility-capacity-index” (RCI), which reflects each country’s share of the global combined responsibility and capability and then assigns shares of the global mitigation effort in proportion to this RCI. The Right to Development (or development need) is taken into consideration by adjusting both capability and responsibility to exempt the incomes and emissions of the poorest from being counted as capability or responsibility of their countries, while – in some variants – counting those of the richest more heavily. Specific operationalizations differ in terms of their time horizon for historical emissions, the thresholds they use to differentiate the poorest and richest and those in-between, and the relative weight given to capability and responsibility, respectively.

Staged Approaches – this concept does not actually refer to any specific allocation approach, rather, it has been introduced as a catch-all category for approaches that apply several of the previously-described approaches differently based on time or circumstances.

Having reviewed the relevant literature and introduced the most important concepts, principles and approaches, the report will now turn toward describing the methodology that was developed to calculate Sweden’s fair share of emissions and mitigation for limiting warming to 1.5 °C, based on these principles and approaches.

3. Methodology

3.1 Selection, quantification and categorization of allocation approaches

3.1.1 Based on literature review and Aurora Request

As discussed, several approaches have been discussed and used within the scholarly literature and by civil society organizations and governments to quantify shares of emissions pathways and/or carbon budgets. Importantly, as also discussed, several approaches are based on principles that have little or no basis in international law or ethical justifications as principles of equity. Many more theoretical allocation approaches exist that emphasize other and/or additional principles for such allocations but have not yet been used for quantifying results.

When selecting allocation approaches for the quantification of fair shares of the RCB or mitigation pathways for this study, several selection criteria have been used. First, for practical reasons, allocation approaches for which a method for calculating shares has not yet been demonstrated in the literature are disregarded. As mentioned above, this likely introduces a systematic bias of the results in favour of high-capability and high-responsibility countries such as Sweden, and, as such, it is likely that results for Sweden would be even more stringent than those presented in this study if those approaches had been included. Second, approaches for which substantial and frequent concerns have been raised in the

⁹ The broader literature refer to the Climate Equity Reference Framework typically by its first specific implementation, the Greenhouse Development Rights, or GDRs (Baer et al. 2007, 2009), whereas its authors prefer the more general “Climate Equity Reference Framework” (Holz et al. 2018).

literature regarding their ethical and/or legal justifications as *equitable* approaches are generally disregarded, although some of them have been calculated for reference only, and their results are provided in the appendix. Those approaches are also categorized as category C, per the taxonomy of Aurora's request (see section 3.1.2 below) and therefore not the focus of this study. Third, allocation approaches that have been routinely used in the literature in the past but have not generally been included in more recent studies are also disregarded, typically because their relevance diminished in the context of changing circumstances and/or their proponents did not continue to develop them.¹⁰ Fourth, for allocation approaches that are conceptually and in terms of their results very similar, a good faith selection of a representative member of the group was made, in order to reduce complexity of the results, while maintaining overall robustness of the approach and the results.

Applying these selection criteria resulted in a set of allocation approaches that includes equal per capita; cumulative equal per capita; variants of both that adjust for capability, variants of both that adjust for capability and needs; the Climate Equity Reference framework (reflecting responsibility, capability, and need); and grandfathering. As mentioned, not all of these approaches are considered "fair" or equitable allocation approaches in this study.

Based on this selection, quantifications were carried out for each of the allocation approaches in this study using two open source software tools, the Fair Shares python package and the Climate Equity Reference Calculator (Holz et al. 2019; Kemp-Benedict et al. 2024), both based on peer-reviewed methodologies, utilizing the most up-to-date authoritative relevant data sources and being used in the scholarly literature, in the context of litigation and by civil society organizations and governments.¹¹ To ensure comparability of results from both software tools, custom input databases for the relevant indicators (GDP, historical emissions, baseline projections, mitigation pathways, population, Gini coefficients) were specifically created for this study to enable both tools to calculate allocations from a shared data base.

The approach of calculating allocations specifically for this study, as opposed to, for example, simply reporting results from the other studies reviewed in the literature review, was chosen for several reasons. First, many of the studies reviewed above do not include results for Sweden. Second, studies differ, often profoundly, in their underlying data sources and concepts, making results difficult to compare across studies without additional data harmonization steps that would require additional assumptions and operations. Third, this approach is established practice in the effort sharing literature, where authors typically use their own implementations of allocation approaches instead of merely utilizing results that have been calculated for previous studies. The specific formulae, algorithms, and concrete

¹⁰ This includes, for example, the Contraction and Convergence approach that was commonly used in the 1990s and early 2000s (Meyer 1999, 2004) but become less in the context of a rapidly shrinking carbon budget, or the South African approach to effort sharing that includes considerations of responsibility, capability and access to sustainable development (Winkler et al. 2011), which has not seen continued development since first proposed.

¹¹ (For the Climate Equity Reference Calculator, see, for example, Adow et al. 2018; African Climate Alliance 2021; CERP 2021; Civil Society Equity Review 2015, 2023, 2024, 2025; FoE US et al. 2021; Holz 2023, 2024b; Holz et al. 2018; Johnston and Tong 2020; Kartha et al. 2021; Kartha, Holz, et al. 2018; RSA 2021, 2025; Sælen et al. 2019; Schäfer et al. 2024; UCT 2025; USCAN 2020).

(For the Fair Shares python package, see, for example, ESABCC 2023; Pelz et al. 2023; Pelz, Ganti, et al. 2025; Pelz, Robiou Du Pont, et al. 2025a, 2025b)

parameterizations used for these calculations represent the author’s good faith application of the conceptual essence of each allocation principle, guided, where applicable, by the Request from Aurora.

Recognizing that these calculations, as well as the selecting and processing of input data sources and of results involves many assumptions and decisions by the researcher and recognizing that, while often appearing as purely methodological choices, these choices are never free of normative content and normative implications, the author made the best effort to transparently document and catalogue all of these choices in the appendix, explaining, where appropriate, the reasoning behind the choice, which alternatives were considered, and the impact on results of the option chosen compared to those not chosen.

3.1.2 Categorization of allocation approaches

According to the Request from Aurora, allocation approaches have been grouped in categories A, B, and C (with “responsibility” defined as including consideration of contributions to cumulative greenhouse gas emissions since at least 1990):

- A. Approaches that factor in states’ differentiated responsibilities **and** respective capabilities.
- B. Approaches that factor in responsibility **or** capability, but not both.
- C. Approaches that factor in **neither** responsibility nor capability.

Detailed results for category C allocation approaches are generally omitted from the main text, but examples are provided in the appendix, results for categories A and B are generally shown in the main text, with more granular results often available in the appendix and with more detailed description and discussion of the results generally focussing on category A.

3.2 Equitable allocation of remaining carbon budgets

3.2.1 General methodology

For calculating Sweden’s fair share of the carbon budget for 1.5°C, the general approach takes as its point of departure the Remaining Carbon Budgets (RCBs) for 1.5°C, with 67% and 83% probability,¹² as calculated by the IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report (IPCC 2021) as updated by Forster et al., which are given as 80 GtCO₂ and 30 GtCO₂ remaining as of 2025, respectively (Forster et al. 2025). Since the present report generally excludes emissions from LULUCF and international bunker fuels from its quantifications of allocations, allowances for these emissions had to be subtracted from the RCBs. The resulting RCBs, excluding LULUCF and bunkers, are 69.2 GtCO₂ and 24.6 GtCO₂ remaining as of 2025, respectively (see Appendix 2 for details).

Due to the fact that RCBs can only sensibly be calculated for carbon dioxide emissions, the budget-based calculations do not consider non-CO₂ greenhouse gases. Calculations were carried out with the Fair Shares python package. Data sources for the calculations include PRIMAP-Hist (Gütschow et al. 2025) for historical emissions, the World Inequality Database for Gini coefficients (WID.world 2024), the United Nations Population Division for population data (United Nations 2022), the IMF World Economic Outlook

¹² Based on Aurora’s request for this report, as reproduced at the beginning of this document.

for GDP (IMF 2024), and the Maddison dataset to extend the IMF GDP time series backwards to 1950 (Maddison 2009; Bolt and Van Zanden 2024, 2025).

All carbon budget allocations are made at a specific point in time. To facilitate this, historical global CO₂ emissions between that point and time and 2025 (the reference year for Forster et al. RCBs) have been added to the RCB prior to allocation. Subsequent to allocation, i.e. after determining Sweden's allocation at that point in time, Sweden's actual emissions between the allocation date and 2025 are subtracted from Sweden's allocation to derive the remaining portion (or overdraft) of Sweden's allocation of the RCB.

3.2.2 Brief description of approaches selected, and parameters chosen

The budget-based fair shares allocation approaches chosen were “equal per capita,” “capacity adjusted equal per capita” and “inequality aware capacity adjusted equal per capita.” Despite the concerns raised in the literature review, equal per capita was used here, because in most of the specific implementations here, it is combined with responsibility by utilizing an allocation date that is sufficiently far in the past and adjusting for actual emissions since the allocation date, which effectively turns the allocation into a “cumulative equal per capita” allocation.

Equal per capita – allocates the remaining carbon budget as of the allocation date to countries proportional to the population of each country, taking into account population changes over time. Here, allocation dates of 1850, 1950, 1990, and 2016 have been used (for a justification of these dates see below), with only the first three reflecting the responsibility principle. The latter two are considered inequitable and inconsistent with the principle of responsibility under the UNFCCC, based on the discussion of equal per capita in the literature. As such, this approach is considered a category B approach for allocation dates in or before 1990, and category C otherwise.

Capacity adjusted equal per capita – taking equal per capita as a starting point, this approach adjusts the equal per capita shares (as described immediately above) according to GDP, where a higher GDP-per-capita results in a lower allocation of the remaining carbon budget. Adjusted values are, again, calculated for allocation dates of 1850, 1950, 1990, and 2016. Other parameters relating to the capacity adjustment are held constant – specifically, the exponent of the adjustment power function is held at -1 and a maximum adjustment impact was not implemented.¹³ This approach is taken to implement the capacity principle, and, if combined with an allocation date of 1990 or earlier, the responsibility principle, in addition to the equality principle. As such, this approach is considered a category A approach for allocation dates in or before 1990, and category B otherwise.

Inequality-aware capacity adjusted equal per capita – the capacity adjustment described immediately above was further adjusted to take into account intra-national inequality (via approximation of income distribution from Gini coefficients), subtracting the incomes below a certain threshold from the capacity of each country. This makes the capacity adjustment stronger in countries with large fractions of the population below this threshold.¹⁴ Allocations are, once again, calculated for allocation dates of 1850, 1950, 1990, and 2016. Other parameters relating to the capacity adjustment are held constant –

13 See Pelz et al. (2023) for a detailed description of the approach and relevant mathematical formulae and appendix 2 for more details on the choices made in the present study.

14 Again, see Pelz et al. (2023) for a detailed description of the approach and relevant mathematical formulae and appendix 2 for more details on the choices made in the present study.

specifically, the exponent of the adjustment power function is held at -1, a maximum to the capacity adjustment was not implemented, an income exemption threshold of \$ 12,500 per person and year is used, and the maximum size of the Gini-based adjustment is held at 50 %.¹⁵ The exemption threshold reflects empirical insights into the intergenerational impacts of poverty (see Appendix 2 for details) and was chosen to match the value used for the effort sharing calculations for mitigation pathways below (see section 3.3.4). Via its exemption of the incomes of the poorest, this approach is taken to implement the Right to Development principle in addition to the capacity principle, and, if combined with an allocation date of 1990 or earlier, the responsibility principle, as well as the equality principle. Like the previous approach, this approach is considered a category A approach for allocation dates in or before 1990, and category B otherwise.

The **selection of time horizons for allocations and for considering past emissions** is considered to cover the breadth of the literature with regards to choices of these dates. In particular, 1850 has been used (e.g., by Jayaraman et al. 2011; Civil Society Equity Review 2015; Pan et al. 2017; Holz et al. 2018; van den Berg et al. 2020; Pelz et al. 2023) to adequately reflect the entirety of the time in which substantial anthropogenic emissions have occurred, with only negligible emissions prior to that date¹⁶ and with practical consideration with regards to data availability for earlier years making this a reasonable time horizon. The justification for using the most complete account of historical emissions as possible is that those emissions, in the case of the long-lived greenhouse gases including CO₂, are still contributing to the build-up of atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations today and therefore have an impact on present generations via climate change and therefore cannot be ignored in a full account of historical responsibility. 1950 has been justified (e.g. by Civil Society Equity Review 2015) as a rough date in which the boundaries of most present nation states have more or less settled in their current place after the end of the Second World War and in the wake of the retreat of European colonial powers from direct colonization in most parts of the world. It is also justified on the grounds that much of the infrastructure, innovations and economic development associated with a marked shift in rates of increase for greenhouse gas emissions at that time (in the context of what has been called “The Great Acceleration,” Steffen et al. 2015) is still benefitting present-day populations in the countries where those emissions occurred. 1990 has been justified as a suitable time horizon (e.g., by Fyson et al. 2020; Ganti et al. 2021; Hahn et al. 2024; Tilsted and Bjørn 2023) as the date in which the publication of the IPCC’s First Assessment Report (Houghton et al. 1990) clarified with a high degree of certainty, and acknowledgement by governments, the role of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions in accelerating global warming and other climate change; marking the first time an intergovernmental body had done so. Additionally, negotiations toward the UNFCCC began in 1990 and the text of the UNFCCC refers to 1990 as an important reference point for mitigation (UNFCCC 1992, Art. 4.2(b)). The choice of 1990 as a relevant time horizon for “historical emissions” has been criticized as being too recent on the basis that the preamble of the UNFCCC refers to “historical emissions,” and that, since it was negotiated between 1990 and 1992, it is implausible to assume that emissions after 1990 would have been considered “historical emissions” from the vantage point of the drafters of the treaty (Civil Society Equity Review 2015). Similarly to 1990, 2016 is justified in relation to the adoption of an international agreement on climate change; in this instance with

15 Explanations of and justification for these methodological choices are provided in Appendix 2.

16 At least in regard to CO₂ emissions from sectors other than LULUCF. Deforestation emissions have been substantial prior to 1850, compared to the negligible amount of emissions from fossil fuel combustion and other industrial uses (Friedlingstein et al. 2025; Gasser and Shrivastav 2023).

reference to the Paris Agreement instead of the UNFCCC, which was adopted in December 2015 (UNFCCC 2015) and came into force in 2016.

3.3 Equitable allocation in the context of mitigation pathways

3.3.1 General methodology

The general approach to calculating national allocations in the context of mitigation pathways takes as its starting point a global mitigation pathway and allocates it – according to any given allocation principle – to countries in such a manner that each country has an allocation pathway, and that the pathways of all countries sum to the total global pathway. As a general principle, this is intended to ensure that countries receive larger or smaller shares of the emissions under the pathway (or larger or smaller shares of the required global mitigation), according to the equity principles of the allocation approach. This means that countries would be required to engage in relatively more or less stringent mitigation to comply with these allocations, again, in accordance with the relevant equity principle.

Figure 1: Stylized comparison between emissions sharing (where, in a given year, a global emissions allowance (green) is shared between countries) and effort sharing (where, in a given year, a global mitigation effort (purple) is shared between countries), both with respect to the same global mitigation pathway (blue).

This report uses two different approaches to allocate the global pathway to individual countries – emissions sharing and effort sharing. Importantly, in both cases, it is the same global pathway that is allocated to countries, in other words, the sum of the national shares will in both cases sum to the same global figures. The main difference between the two approaches is how they conceptualize what it is that is shared between countries. In the case of emissions sharing, the emissions allowed under the global pathway curve are shared (which are sometimes considered a common resource, hence the term “resource sharing” is also used). In contrast, for effort sharing, the difference between a no-effort baseline projection (or another reference level) and the global pathway – i.e. the global mitigation effort – is shared between countries. This reflects different fundamental ethical positions with regards to the issue at hand (whether mitigation pathways represent a diminishing resource or an increasing effort) but – in terms of global figures – has the same result. Figure 1 illustrates this difference between emissions sharing and

effort sharing; figures 3 and 4 below illustrate more specifically how national pathway allocations are derived in each case.

Specifically, for calculating Sweden's fair share of global 1.5°C consistent mitigation, scenarios were selected from the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report scenario database (Byers et al. 2022; IPCC 2022), in a version that has been updated to reflect data in countries' national inventory reports (Gidden et al. 2023a, 2023b). Specifically, as per Aurora's request for this report, scenarios have been selected that are classified by the IPCC to belong to category C1 – pathways with low or no overshoot of 1.5°C. This selection has been further filtered for those among the "C1" pathways that have at least a 67% or 83% probability (C1₆₇, and C1₈₃), respectively, for temperatures to be 1.5°C or lower in 2100.

Again, the Fair Shares python package was used for calculations for "emissions sharing" approaches, with the same data sources as described in section 3.2 above. Again, LULUCF and international bunker fuels are not part of the calculations, though non-CO₂ greenhouse gases are now included. To this end, detailed pathway data for each of the scenarios in the C1₆₇, and C1₈₃ subcategories have been obtained from the IPCC's AR6 Scenario Database and Explorer (Byers et al. 2022) including the subsequent update from Gidden et al. (2023b) that aligns the scenario data with countries' emissions inventory data as submitted to the UNFCCC. From this pathway data, time series with emissions and removals from LULUCF have been excluded for all scenarios; with all other emissions and removals remaining in the scenario data used here as net emissions.

For calculations for "effort sharing" approaches, the Climate Equity Reference Calculator (Holz et al. 2019; Kemp-Benedict et al. 2024) has been used. To achieve comparability of results between the two software tools, the Climate Equity Reference Calculator has been configured to use the same input data as the Fair Shares python package, with the exception of the no-effort baseline, which is required for calculations with the Climate Equity Reference Calculator but not the Fair Shares package. No-effort baselines were calculated using the methodology outlined in the Calculator's documentation (Holz et al. 2024), but using the data sources enumerated above, as opposed to those described in the documentation.

3.3.2 Adjustment for shortfall relative to initial allocation in the recent past

After initial allocations are calculated based on each of the selected allocation approaches, these allocations are adjusted according to the amounts of actual emissions that were emitted in the most recent history in excess of the initial allocation for the period. This ensures that the impact of countries' failure to satisfy the limits of their emissions allocations (i.e. the "shortfall") is borne by each country, as opposed to being socialized to all countries collectively. Here, the shortfall between initial allocation and actual emissions is calculated for the years 2016-2025, reflecting the time since the adoption of the Paris Agreement. The justification for this approach considers that countries, in adopting the Paris Agreement, committed to collectively implement its objectives, based on equity and CBDRRC, and that the initial allocation reflects their share of this commitment. To the degree that a shortfall between this allocation and their actual emissions exists, it reflects a failure to honour that commitment, and it would be inappropriate to simply ignore this failure. Hence, this approach ensures that countries continue to be held responsible to their allocation as calculated from the adoption of the Paris Agreement, rather than only considering them for the future. In other words, "shortfall" is not used to determine the allocation, but rather to make adjustments to it after the initial allocation. The cumulative shortfall is then applied to

adjust the allocation over the 2026-2045 period, with equal fractions of the total added to each year. Figure 2 shows a stylized example of this adjustment to a country's allocations.

While this is similar in nature to considering responsibility in allocation approaches, it is different from the concept of responsibility in important ways. Given that only the most recent past is considered, the “shortfall” does not represent “historical responsibility” in the typical sense, which implies time horizons with much deeper history, and which is used in initial allocations, rather than adjusting allocations after their initial calculation. The advantage of this approach is that an initial allocation can be calculated based on any specific allocation approach (which may or may not include considerations of responsibility) and this adjustment then ensures that allocations (at least since the time of the adoption of the Paris Agreement) remain aligned with the allocation approach, instead of increasingly diverging from it as time passes.

Figure 2: Stylized approach of applying recent history shortfall to near future allocations.

3.3.3 Emissions sharing

Emissions sharing allocates the net emissions under an emissions pathway to countries according to the selected allocation principle.¹⁷ Figure 3 illustrates this approach: the emissions under a global mitigation pathway are distributed according to an allocation approach so that the national shares sum to the global pathway.

The Fair Shares python package is used to calculate the allocations. The same approaches as described in section 3.2.2 were used. However, the “equal per capita” approach as applied to pathways does not yield different allocations for different allocation start dates. This is because the cumulative aspect that characterizes budget-sharing does not apply to allocations under emissions pathways. Thus, unlike for the budget-based equal per capita approach, where early start dates effectively rendered an “equal per capita” allocation into a “cumulative equal per capita” allocation (which respects the responsibility principle), there is no version that reflects the responsibility principle.

Therefore, there is no category A approach among the emissions sharing approaches quantified here. The capacity adjusted equal per capita allocation (with or without inequality awareness) are considered category B approaches, as they reflect the Capability (and, where applicable, Need) principle. Without the capacity adjustment, the equal per capita approach used here is considered a category C approach.

¹⁷ In other words, any emissions or removals under the pathway are allocated jointly, not separately. As discussed previously, recently, studies have begun to articulate reasons why allocation of removals should be considered separate (and potentially differently) than allocation of emissions.

Figure 3: Stylized approach of emissions sharing in the context of a global mitigation pathway, where the total global emissions under the pathway (panel a) are allocated to individual countries based on allocation principles (panel b), yielding individual allocation pathways for countries (panel c)

Following the discussion in the literature review, the emissions sharing approach implemented here does not utilize transition periods that start from grandfathered emissions levels, but instead applies each allocation approach immediately.

3.3.4 Effort sharing

Effort sharing allocates a global mitigation effort to countries according to the selected allocation approach – figure 4 illustrates the approach. Here, the total global mitigation effort refers to the difference between a global no-effort baseline and the global emissions pathways of the C1₆₇ and C1₈₃ scenario ensembles (panel a of figure 4). This global effort is shared among countries according to allocation approaches (panel b). Each country’s share of the effort is then applied to the national no-effort baseline of each country to yield the country’s pathway (panel c).

For the effort sharing calculations, the Climate Equity Reference Calculator has been used. As described in the literature review, the Climate Equity Reference Framework is based on the Responsibility-Capacity-Index (RCI), which calculates each country’s share of the combined global responsibility and capability, as per users’ specific definitions. To calculate the RCI, the cumulative emissions from a given start date are calculated for each country and then expressed as a fraction of the global cumulative emissions. Likewise, for the capacity calculations, a country’s capability (measured, in the first instance, as GDP) is expressed as the fraction of the total global capability for a given year. The global mitigation effort is then allocated in proportion to the RCI. In other words, if a country has, for example, 25% of the total responsibility (i.e. its cumulative emissions are 25% of the global cumulative emissions) and 25% of the total capability (i.e. its capability is 25% of the total global capability), then its RCI is 25% and it would be assigned 25% of the global effort.

Importantly, both capability and responsibility are adjusted to exempt the incomes and emissions of the poorest from being counted as capability or responsibility of their countries, while – in some variants (“High Progressivity,” see below) – counting those of the richest more heavily. This is done by modeling an income distribution for each country and year based on the country’s GDP and the Gini coefficient and then excluding the incomes below a certain threshold from being counted as capability, and excluding the

emissions associated with consumption below this threshold from being counted as responsibility, following Shue’s assertion that survival emissions and luxury emissions ought to be treated differently (Shue 1993).¹⁸

Figure 4: Stylized approach of effort sharing in the context of a global mitigation pathway, where the total global mitigation effort is defined as the difference between a global no-effort baseline and the mitigation pathway emissions (panel a). This total global mitigation effort is allocated to individual countries based on allocation principles (panel b), yielding individual shares of the global effort for countries that are then subtracted from the countries’ no-effort baseline to yield the countries’ emissions allocation (panel c). Countries’ emissions allocations sum to the global mitigation pathway and countries’ no-effort baselines sum to the global no-effort baseline.

Here, a number of different operationalizations of the RCI have been used. First, with regards to the capability component of the RCI, capability was expressed in terms of “high progressivity” and “medium progressivity,” following established practice of the Civil Society Equity Review (initially in Civil Society Equity Review 2015) and others. The “development threshold” value used by the Civil Society Equity Review has been updated to \$12,500 to reflect inflation.¹⁹ Responsibility is expressed as cumulative historical emissions from start dates of 1850, 1950, 1990, and 2016. Combining the four start dates with two approaches to progressivity yields eight different parameterizations of the Climate Equity Reference Framework. All of these combinations use equal weights for responsibility and capability. For responsibility start dates in 1990 or before, these combinations are considered category A allocation approaches, category B for 2016 start dates.

Additionally, variants have been calculated that disregard either capability or responsibility, by using a weight of zero for the disregarded component. The resulting “capability only” approaches also use “high” and “medium” progressivity and the resulting “responsibility only” approaches use start dates of 1850, 1950, 1990 and 2016. These approaches are considered category B approaches, with the exception of the one using a 2016 start date, which is category C.

18 For more details, see Holz et al. (2018) and Kemp-Benedict et al. (2018).

19 The Civil Society Equity Review and other users utilize a development threshold of \$7,500 (in 2005 PPP USD). The rationale for this level is explained elsewhere (Holz et al. 2018; Civil Society Equity Review 2015). Here, a higher level of \$12,500 is used because the database used with the Climate Equity Reference Calculator for the present report uses current PPP dollars, as opposed to the 2005 PPP dollars. \$12,500 in current PPP dollars is the approximate equivalent of \$7,500 in 2005 PPP dollars.

4. Results

This section presents the results of most of the allocations calculated in this study. Generally, this section focuses on Category A allocation approaches, though results for Category B approaches are also sometimes presented. Furthermore, for simplicity, and because the results are very similar, for allocations in the context of mitigation pathways, generally only results for the C1₆₇ pathways are presented here. Appendix 1 contains additional results – for example, for additional Category B approaches as well as come Category C approaches, and for the C1₈₃ pathways, in the case of allocations in the context of mitigation pathways.

Results generally assume a territorial emissions accounting approach, where emissions are considered the responsibility of a country if they were emitted from its territory. This is different, chiefly, from consumption-based accounting, where a country's responsibility is instead considered to be the emissions associated with the production of the goods and services that its residents consume. Territorial accounting is the standard used by the UNFCCC and most governments, including Sweden, though there are important ethical reasons why consumption-based accounting may be preferable. Further, where non-CO₂ GHGs are included in results, they were converted to CO₂-equivalents using the 100-year Global Warming Potentials from the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (IPCC 2021).

4.1 Equitable allocation of remaining carbon budgets

Table 2 shows the results of the main allocation approaches for carbon budgets as introduced above, with regards to the remaining carbon budget for 1.5 °C (RCB_{1.5}).²⁰ The results show clearly that, for category A allocation approaches, the most impactful equity parameter is the time horizon from which historical responsibility for cumulative greenhouse gas emissions is considered. That is, comparing between “capacity adjusted” and “inequality-aware capacity adjusted” allocations with the same responsibility time horizon (regardless of whether that is 1950 or 1990) shows less difference in the size of the budget overdraft than comparing between responsibility start dates within the same allocation approach.

Likewise, the chosen probability for the temperature increase (67 % vs. 83 % – reflected in the results ranges for each line in the table) has less impact on the results than the responsibility start date or the way in which capability is considered. This latter effect is easily understood recalling the extremely small size of the remaining carbon budget.

For category A allocation approaches, then, i.e. those approaches that take both responsibility and capability sufficiently into account, the **size of Sweden's overdraft with regards to the RCB_{1.5} is at least 1,630 MtCO₂ and as high as 4,590 MtCO₂**, among the approaches quantified here. Specifically, for parameterizations of category A approaches that consider historical responsibility for cumulative greenhouse gas concentrations from a 1950 start date, Sweden's overdraft of RCB_{1.5} is in the range of 4,563 to 4,590 MtCO₂, depending on the specific operationalization of capability and the probability of the 1.5 °C warming outcome. For all category A approaches that are shown in the table, results range from 1,630 to 4,587 MtCO₂ overdrawn for RCB_{1.5} with 67% probability and from 1,637 to 4,590 MtCO₂ overdrawn for RCB_{1.5}

²⁰ Recall from section 3.2.1 above that the RCBs used here, i.e. excluding LULUCF and bunkers, are 69.2 GtCO₂ and 24.6 GtCO₂ remaining as of 2025, respectively for 67 % and 83 % probability.

with 83% probability. For category B approaches, results range from 269 to 3,606 MtCO₂, depending on the specific allocation approach and the probability of the warming outcome.

Allocation Approach	Budget Remaining (as of Jan 1, 2026) (MtCO₂)	Budget Overdrawn by (as of Jan 1, 2026) (MtCO₂)	Equity Principles
<i>Category A - Approaches Reflecting Both Responsibility and Capability</i>			
Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (1950)	---	4,563 – 4,567	Responsibility, Capability
Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (1990)	---	1,630 – 1,637	Responsibility, Capability
Inequality Aware Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (1950)	---	4,587 – 4,590	Responsibility, Capability, Need
Inequality Aware Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (1990)	---	1,703 – 1,707	Responsibility, Capability, Need
<i>Category B - Approaches Reflecting either Responsibility or Capability but not both</i>			
Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (2016)	---	269 – 283	Capability
Inequality Aware Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (2016)	---	319 – 328	Capability, Need
Equal Per Capita (1850)	---	3,537 – 3,606	Equality, Responsibility
Equal Per Capita (1950)	---	2,461 – 2,520	Equality, Responsibility
Equal Per Capita (1990)	---	461 – 515	Equality, Responsibility

Table 2: Results for the main approaches for allocation of remaining carbon budgets to Sweden (CO₂ only, exclusive of LULUCF), as of January 1, 2026, for categories A and B. Ranges for results reflect the difference between allocating RCBs for 67% and 83% probability of 1.5 °C, respectively. Year numbers in parenthesis indicate the year in which the remaining budget (as of that date) was allocated. Also shows applicable equity principles. More detailed results (including initial budget allocation and their adjustments for past emissions) as well as results for category C approaches are in Table A-1 in the Appendix.

This clearly indicates that regardless of specific choice of fair share allocation approaches and their parameterization, Sweden not only has no entitlement to the remaining carbon budget but also has accrued a substantial carbon debt, the resolution of which is an integral part of its fair contribution to a global response to remain within RCB_{1.5}.

The results also show that even for the category B allocation approaches, i.e. those approaches that ignore either responsibility or capability (but not both), Sweden's share of the RCB_{1.5} is a substantial overdraft, though, in most cases, it is substantially smaller than for approaches in category A. This is especially evident for approaches that only consider differentiated capabilities and disregard responsibility altogether, or that disregard capability and use the most restrictive definition of responsibility (1990 start date).

The results for categories A and B taken together clearly show that the finding that Sweden has no entitlement to RCB_{1.5} and instead a substantial carbon debt, are robust even when some of the fundamental equity principles are ignored. In fact (not shown in the table above, but contained in the appendix), only when *both* capability and responsibility are disregarded (category C approaches) can positive allocations be calculated, though in most cases they would be exhausted in less than five years of emissions at current trends.

4.2 Equitable allocation in the context of mitigation pathways

As discussed above, equitable allocation in respect to a mitigation pathway here follows two distinct classes of approaches. The first class of approaches calculates equitable allocations of the emissions that occur under a mitigation pathway whereas the second class of approaches allocated the mitigation effort required, relative to baseline projections_{1.5}, to achieve the mitigation pathway. Results for both will be shown and discussed in turn.

For both approaches, the shortfall between the allocation and the actual emissions of the recent past (since 2016) are calculated and this shortfall is applied to the near term (to 2045) of allocations to

compensate for this shortfall. This ensures that the cumulative allocation remains constant over the 2016 to 2045 period, despite actual emissions between 2016 and 2025 having exceeded the allocation. Figure 2 in section 3.3.2 shows this approach for a stylized case: panel a shows historical emissions until 2025 (black) and the initial allocation (red), panel b shows the shortfall as the difference between them (red area), panel c shows how this shortfall is applied to the initial allocation to derive the shortfall-adjusted allocation (the sizes of the red area in panels b and c are identical), panel d shows the resulting short-fall adjusted allocation. For simplicity, the results in the main text will only show charts for the initial allocations as well as the shortfall-adjusted allocations (i.e. the equivalents of panels a and d in figure 2).

Before turning to results for allocations, it is important to recall that great care needs to be taken in the interpretation of pathways allocations that only consider part of the overall time horizon of the pathway – namely, considering only the portion up to 2045 of a pathway that spans the entire remainder of the century. Specifically, the pathways of the C1 category in the IPCC AR6 scenario ensemble all assume an overshoot of 1.5°C of warming, caused by excess greenhouse gas emissions in the near term, which is then assumed to be compensated by substantial amounts of carbon dioxide removal in later decades, especially in the second half of the century. As mentioned above, equitable allocation of this carbon dioxide removal effort raises additional, and potentially different, equity concerns as the allocation of positive emissions or other mitigation efforts, though they are beyond the scope of the present study.

This makes allocations of emissions under a pathway much different from the allocations of the RCB, where only emissions are allocated up to the point at which the temperature outcome associated with the RCB is reached. RCBs are therefore, per their definition, consistent with the stated temperature objective. The near-term emissions trajectories of emissions pathways, on the other hand, are consistent with the stated temperature objective only if the carbon dioxide removal that is assumed to take place later during the pathway’s trajectory actually materializes. If it does not, then the stated temperature objective will not be met. From an equitable-effort-sharing perspective this is relevant because by this feature, pathways allow relatively less stringent mitigation in the near term than RCBs imply, but in turn they imply committing future generations to implementing carbon dioxide removal at least at the assumed level, with important implications for intergenerational equity.²¹

4.2.1 Emissions sharing

For emissions sharing, calculations for the selected allocation approaches were done separately for the C1₆₇ and C1₈₃ pathways. The results for the C1₈₃ pathways are very similar to those of the C1₆₇ pathways (since C1₈₃ is a subset of C1₆₇) and, for simplicity, are therefore omitted from the figures and tables below. For completeness, a set of charts and tables for the C1₈₃ pathways are contained in the appendix.

Figure 5 shows results for the selected emissions sharing allocation approaches. As discussed above, these approaches do not take responsibility into account and are therefore not part of category A of equitable allocation approaches. The allocation approaches imply a total equivalent emission reduction below 1990 levels of 96% to 98% in 2030, 98% to 99% in 2035 and 99% in 2045. These allocations are very low because, compared to the countries where the majority of the global population lives, Sweden

21 Additionally, this feature implies at least temporary overshoot of the temperature objective, with profound increase in risks of climate impacts, which carry additional implications for international, intergenerational and interspecies justice, which are, however, beyond the scope of this study.

has a very high capability (measured in per-capita GDP), which, for allocation approaches that allocate larger amounts to countries with lower capability, implies a small allocation for Sweden, to accommodate with these amounts.

Figure 5: Results for the allocation under the C1₆₇ pathway for the capacity-adjusted equal per capita approach (with allocations starting in 1950 and 1990, respectively) and for the inequality-aware capacity adjusted equal per capita approach (with a \$2000-, and \$12,500-income threshold). Allocations are not adjusted for near history shortfall. Percentages express allocations in terms of total reductions below 1990 levels.

When considering Sweden’s shortfall of Sweden’s actual emissions over the 2015-2025 period relative to the allocation, and when applying this shortfall to the next 20 years of climate ambition, the described effects are substantially changed by this adjustment. Specifically, as shown in figure 6 and table 3, according to these Category B allocation approaches, allocations of emissions under the pathway C1₆₇ are an equivalent of an emissions reduction below 1990 levels of 127% to 131% in 2030, 129% to 131% in 2035 and 130% to 132% in 2045.²²

The appendix contains a version of table 3 (table A-2), that adds results for an equal per capita allocation, which is a Category C allocation approach because it takes neither capability nor responsibility into account.

²² This corresponds to emissions allowances of -19.6 to -22.0 MtCO₂eq in 2030, -20.6 to -22.4 MtCO₂eq in 2035 and -21.4 to -22.8 MtCO₂eq in 2045 (excluding LULUCF).

Figure 6: Results for the same set of allocation approaches as figure 5, with allocations adjusted for near history shortfall. Results for the C1₈₃ pathway are in the appendix.

Allocation Approach	Reductions in % below 1990 by (before adjustment)			Reductions in % below 1990 by (with adjustment)			Equity Principles
	2030	2035	2045	2030	2035	2045	
<i>Category B - Approaches Reflecting either Responsibility or Capability but not both</i>							
Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (1950)	96 %	98 %	99 %	127 %	129 %	130 %	Capability, Need
Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (1990)	97 %	98 %	99 %	128 %	129 %	130 %	Capability, Need
Inequality-Aware Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (\$2000)	98 %	99 %	99 %	130 %	131 %	131 %	Capability
Inequality-Aware Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita (\$12500)	98 %	99 %	99 %	131 %	131 %	132 %	Capability

Table 3: Results for the allocation under the C1₆₇ pathway for the capacity-adjusted equal per capita approach (with allocations starting in 1950 and 1990, respectively) and for the inequality-aware capacity adjusted equal per capita approach (with a \$2000-, and \$12,500-income threshold). Allocations are shown for before (left) and after (right) adjustment for near history shortfall. Percentages represent equivalent of reductions below 1990 levels and refer to greenhouse gas emissions exclusive of LULUCF.

4.2.2 Effort sharing

Figure 7 shows the results of the effort sharing calculations of the Climate Equity Reference Framework (CERf) allocation approach, before the adjustment for recent shortfall relative to fair shares allocations. It shows the results for four values for the start date for the counting of emissions (1850, 1950, 1990, 2016), each in combination with two possible parameterizations of capability (“High Progressivity” and “Medium Progressivity” – see Appendix 2 for more detailed descriptions of these parameterizations). Figure 8 shows the results for the same parameterizations of the CERf, except with adjustments made for the shortfall between the fair share allocation and actual emissions in the most recent past. Note that the allocations that use 2016 as start date for counting emissions are not considered category A allocations in this study.

In both sets of results, as already observed for other allocation approaches, allocations for Sweden are more stringent with a longer time horizon for historical responsibility. Furthermore, for each start date for historical responsibility, generally the “high progressivity” operationalization of the capability component yields more stringent results than “medium progressivity.”

Figure 7: Results for the allocation of the global mitigation effort required under the C1₆₇ pathway for selected Climate Equity Reference Framework allocation approaches. Allocations are not adjusted for near history shortfall. Percentages express allocations in terms of total reductions below 1990 levels. Results for the C1₈₃ pathway are in the appendix (figure A-3).

After adjustment for shortfall, the CERf results (category A only) for **Sweden’s fair share of global mitigation effort required for the C1₆₇ 1.5°C mitigation pathway ranges from 154 to 173% reduction below 1990 levels in 2030, 207 to 230% in 2035 and 270 to 302% in 2045.**²³

The CERf can also be parameterized to disregard capability or responsibility in the calculations, thus providing additional results for category B allocation approaches. In addition to the approaches shown in the figures above, table 4 below summarizes the results for “capability only” and “responsibility only” approaches, utilizing the same parametrizations of responsibility for emissions as above (1850, 1950, 1990, 2016) as well as of capability (“high” and “medium” progressivity).

²³ This corresponds to emissions allowances of -38.8 to -52.3 MtCO₂eq in 2030, -77.0 to -93.7 MtCO₂eq in 2035 and -122.5 to -145.2 MtCO₂eq in 2045 (excluding LULUCF).

Figure 8: Results for the same set of allocation approaches as figure 7, with allocations adjusted for near history shortfall. Results for the C1₈₃ pathway are in the appendix (figure A-4).

Progressivity Approach	Emissions Responsibility Start Date	Reductions in % below 1990 by (before adjustment)			Reductions in % below 1990 by (with adjustment)			Equity Principles
		2030	2035	2045	2030	2035	2045	
Category A - Approaches Reflecting Both Responsibility and Capability								
High Progressivity	1850	149 %	204 %	270 %	158 %	213 %	280 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
	1950	149 %	205 %	271 %	159 %	214 %	280 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
	1990	145 %	198 %	262 %	154 %	207 %	270 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
Medium Progressivity	1850	161 %	218 %	290 %	172 %	229 %	301 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
	1950	162 %	219 %	291 %	173 %	230 %	302 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
	1990	152 %	205 %	270 %	162 %	215 %	280 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
Category B - Approaches Reflecting either Responsibility or Capability but not both								
High Progr.	2016	137 %	184 %	243 %	146 %	192 %	251 %	Capability, Need
Medium Progr.	2016	138 %	183 %	240 %	146 %	192 %	249 %	Capability, Need
High Progr.	responsibility	212 %	302 %	432 %	228 %	317 %	447 %	Capability, Need
Medium Progr.	not considered	221 %	309 %	432 %	238 %	326 %	449 %	Capability, Need
capacity not considered	1850	108 %	143 %	185 %	113 %	147 %	189 %	Responsibility
	1950	115 %	151 %	195 %	120 %	156 %	201 %	Responsibility
	1990	88 %	114 %	147 %	91 %	117 %	150 %	Responsibility

Table 4: Results for the allocation of the global mitigation effort required under the C1₆₇ pathway for selected Climate Equity Reference Framework allocation approaches. Allocations are shown for before (left) and after (right) adjustment for near history shortfall. Percentages represent equivalent of reductions below 1990 levels and refer to greenhouse gas emissions exclusive of LULUCF. A version of this table with results shown additionally as emissions allocations is in the appendix (table A-3); results for the C1₈₃ pathway are also in the appendix (table A-4).

5. Discussion

The results clearly show that under all assessed fair share allocation approaches that are consistent with Aurora's request – i.e. that satisfy reasonable minimum standards of fairness and are consistent with limiting warming to 1.5°C –, there is a very significant gap between Sweden's fair share and Sweden's current mitigation measures. In fact, even if Sweden ceased any emission of greenhouse gases

immediately, it would continue to fall short of those fair share allocation requirements. This is true for both budget allocation approaches as well as for pathway-based approaches.

For budget approaches, Sweden not only has no fair share entitlement to the remaining global carbon budget for 1.5 °C, it also has substantially overdrawn its share of the global carbon budget by emitting substantially above its entitlement in the past. Non-overdrawn results can only be calculated for Sweden when equity considerations are relaxed to such a substantial degree that the resulting allocation cannot be reasonably defended as fair anymore (i.e. using “grandfathering”). However, even in those cases – in addition to being inequitable – that budget tends to be miniscule and only sufficient for a very few years at present emissions levels.

Similarly, for pathway-based approaches, even before adjusting for Sweden’s excess emissions since the adoption of the Paris Agreement, emissions reductions for 2030, 2035 and 2045 are substantially in excess of 100 % for allocation approaches consistent with Aurora’s request. Again, when equity considerations are relaxed substantially, allocations can be calculated that, in 2030 and before adjustment, yield results lower than 100 %, but once adjustments are applied and/or reductions for the year 2035 are considered instead of 2030, all approaches – even blatantly inequitable ones – imply emissions reductions in excess of 100 %.

This points to the general conclusion that, in all cases, Sweden’s fair share of the mitigation effort that is globally required to limit warming to 1.5 °C far exceeds the mitigation that can be implemented on Sweden’s territory alone. This, in turn, points to the need for Sweden to not only substantially increase the mitigation effort within its own territory but also to its responsibility for ensuring a substantial amount of additional mitigation outside its territory. Importantly, as the results suggest, this “extra-territorial” mitigation is in most cases at least as large as, and often much larger than, the amount of mitigation needed domestically. In other words, the attention and scale of extra-territorial mitigation ought to at least match that of domestic mitigation.²⁴

Taken together, while – as just discussed – the results have very clear implications regarding the minimum level of Sweden’s fair share mitigation contribution, they nevertheless span a substantial range of possible sizes of Sweden’s fair share depending on specific normative assumptions. Importantly, for each level of ambition from this range, it is crucial to consider what that ambition level means for the global mitigation and for the mitigation required in all other countries. Specifically, if all countries would simply choose the approach that is most lenient for them, global mitigation would be insufficient, and the temperature limit would be exceeded (Meinshausen et al. 2015; Rajamani et al. 2021; UCT 2021, 2025). Alternatively, if a country would simply choose the most lenient-for-them approach, then, in conjunction with the global temperature limitation objective and the underlying allocation principle, this also determines the reduction targets for all other countries. And those targets may not only be unfair, but also unrealistic, given countries’ capabilities, thus, again, placing the 1.5 °C objective in jeopardy.

24 Such extra-territorial mitigation can be implemented via provision of mitigation finance (bilaterally or through multilateral funds including the Green Climate Fund), potentially the use of cooperative mechanisms as outlined in Article 6 of the Paris Agreement, or other approaches to cooperation and support. Theoretically, some of this could also be implemented via Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) activities, though substantial concerns exist with regards to sustainability, economic and social considerations as well as with regards to the limited scale of such activities, as has been discussed above.

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Appendix 1: More Detailed Results

(all amounts in MtCO₂)								
Allocation Approach	Allocation Start Date	Initial Budget Allocation		Emissions from Start Date to 2025	Remaining Budget as of Jan 1, 2026		Equity Principle	Category
		66%	83%		66%	83%		
<i>Category A - Approaches Reflecting Both Responsibility and Capability</i>								
Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita	1950	139	135	4,702	-4,563	-4,567	Responsibility, Capability	A
Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita	1990	167	161	1,797	-1,630	-1,637	Responsibility, Capability	A
Inequality Aware Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita	1950	116	113	4,702	-4,587	-4,590	Responsibility, Capability, Need	A
Inequality Aware Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita	1990	94	90	1,797	-1,703	-1,707	Responsibility, Capability, Need	A
<i>Category B - Approaches Reflecting either Responsibility or Capability but not both</i>								
Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita	2016	124	110	393	-269	-283	Capability	B
Inequality Aware Capacity Adjusted Equal Per Capita	2016	74	65	393	-319	-328	Capability, Need	B
Equal Per Capita	1850	2,976	2,907	6,513	-3,537	-3,606	Equality, Responsibility	B
Equal Per Capita	1950	2,241	2,182	4,702	-2,461	-2,520	Equality, Responsibility	B
Equal Per Capita	1990	1,336	1,282	1,797	-461	-515	Equality, Responsibility	B
<i>Category C - Approaches Reflecting neither Responsibility nor Capability</i>								
Equal Per Capita	2016	454	402	393	61	9	none/Equality*	C
Grandfathering (0.26%)	1990	2,843	2,728	1,797	1,046	931	none	C
Grandfathering (0.12%)	2016	484	428	393	91	35	none	C

Table A-1: Detailed results and calculations for the main allocation approaches of remaining carbon budgets, showing initial allocation by probability of climate outcome (“budget allocation”), historical emissions from the allocation date to 2025 and the “remaining budget as of Jan 1, 2026” as the difference between initial allocation and historical emissions (positive numbers) or overdrawn budget as of Jan 1, 2026 (negative numbers). Also shows applicable equity principles and the resulting assignment to categories A-C.

Allocation Approach	Reductions in % below 1990 by and Allocation in Mt CO₂ eq in (before adjustment)			Reductions in % below 1990 by and Allocation in Mt CO₂ eq in (with adjustment)			Equity Principles	Category
	2030	2035	2045	2030	2035	2045		
<i>Category B - Approaches Reflecting either Responsibility or Capability but not both</i>								
Capacity Adjusted	96 %	98 %	99 %	127 %	129 %	130 %	Capability, Need	B
Equal Per Capita (1950)	2.6 Mt	1.7 Mt	0.9 Mt	-19.6 Mt	-20.6 Mt	-21.4 Mt	Capability, Need	B
Capacity Adjusted	97 %	98 %	99 %	128 %	129 %	130 %	Capability, Need	B
Equal Per Capita (1990)	2.2 Mt	1.4 Mt	0.7 Mt	-20.3 Mt	-21.1 Mt	-21.8 Mt	Capability, Need	B
Inequality-Aware Capacity Adjusted	98 %	99 %	99 %	130 %	131 %	131 %	Capability	B
Inequality-Aware Capacity Adjusted	1.4 Mt	0.9 Mt	0.5 Mt	-21.6 Mt	-22.1 Mt	-22.5 Mt	Capability	B
Inequality-Aware Capacity Adjusted	98 %	99 %	99 %	131 %	131 %	132 %	Capability	B
Inequality-Aware Capacity Adjusted	1.1 Mt	0.7 Mt	0.4 Mt	-22.0 Mt	-22.4 Mt	-22.8 Mt	Capability	B
<i>Category C - Approaches Reflecting neither Responsibility nor Capability</i>								
Equal Per Capita	37 %	61 %	81 %	n/a	n/a	n/a	none/Equality*	C
Equal Per Capita	45.7 Mt	27.9 Mt	13.6 Mt	n/a	n/a	n/a	none/Equality*	C

Table A-2: Detailed results (in terms of percentage reduction as well as emissions allocations in MtCO₂) for category B and C emissions allocation approaches. See caption of table 3 for more details.

Figure A-1: Results for the same set of allocation approaches as figure 5, here for the C1₈₃ subset of mitigation scenarios.

Figure A-2: Results for the same set of allocation approaches as figure 6, here for the C1₈₃ subset of mitigation scenarios.

Figure A-3: Results for the same set of allocation approaches as figure 7, here for the C1₈₃ subset of mitigation scenarios.

Figure A-4: Results for the same set of allocation approaches as figure 8, here for the C1₈₃ subset of mitigation scenarios.

Progressivity Approach	Emissions Responsibility Start Date	Reductions in % below 1990 by and Allocation in Mt CO ₂ eq in (before adjustment)			Reductions in % below 1990 by and Allocation in Mt CO ₂ eq in (with adjustment)			Equity Principles
		2030	2035	2045	2030	2035	2045	
		Category A - Approaches Reflecting Both Responsibility and Capability						
High Progressivity	1850	149 %	204 %	270 %	158 %	213 %	280 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-35.3 Mt	-75.0 Mt	-122.6 Mt	-41.9 Mt	-81.6 Mt	-129.2 Mt	
	1950	149 %	205 %	271 %	159 %	214 %	280 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-35.5 Mt	-75.3 Mt	-122.8 Mt	-42.1 Mt	-81.9 Mt	-129.4 Mt	
	1990	145 %	198 %	262 %	154 %	207 %	270 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-32.5 Mt	-70.8 Mt	-116.2 Mt	-38.8 Mt	-77.0 Mt	-122.5 Mt	
Medium Progressivity	1850	161 %	218 %	290 %	172 %	229 %	301 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-43.9 Mt	-85.2 Mt	-136.9 Mt	-51.7 Mt	-93.1 Mt	-144.7 Mt	
	1950	162 %	219 %	291 %	173 %	230 %	302 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-44.4 Mt	-85.8 Mt	-137.3 Mt	-52.3 Mt	-93.7 Mt	-145.2 Mt	
	1990	152 %	205 %	270 %	162 %	215 %	280 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-37.4 Mt	-75.6 Mt	-122.1 Mt	-44.5 Mt	-82.8 Mt	-129.2 Mt	
Category B - Approaches Reflecting either Responsibility or Capability but not both								
High Progr.	2016	137 %	184 %	243 %	146 %	192 %	251 %	Capability, Need
		-27.0 Mt	-60.5 Mt	-103.2 Mt	-32.8 Mt	-66.3 Mt	-109.0 Mt	
Medium Progr.	2016	138 %	183 %	240 %	146 %	192 %	249 %	Capability, Need
		-27.2 Mt	-59.8 Mt	-100.9 Mt	-33.3 Mt	-66.0 Mt	-107.0 Mt	
High Progr.	responsibility not considered	212 %	302 %	432 %	228 %	317 %	447 %	Capability, Need
		-80.7 Mt	-145.0 Mt	-238.8 Mt	-91.9 Mt	-156.3 Mt	-250.0 Mt	
Medium Progr.	responsibility not considered	221 %	309 %	432 %	238 %	326 %	449 %	Capability, Need
		-86.9 Mt	-150.1 Mt	-239.0 Mt	-99.3 Mt	-162.5 Mt	-251.3 Mt	
capacity not considered	1850	108 %	143 %	185 %	113 %	147 %	189 %	Responsibility
		-5.6 Mt	-30.6 Mt	-60.8 Mt	-9.0 Mt	-34.0 Mt	-64.3 Mt	
	1950	115 %	151 %	195 %	120 %	156 %	201 %	Responsibility
		-10.5 Mt	-36.4 Mt	-68.3 Mt	-14.7 Mt	-40.6 Mt	-72.5 Mt	
	1990	88 %	114 %	147 %	91 %	117 %	150 %	Responsibility
		8.5 Mt	-10.1 Mt	-33.7 Mt	6.4 Mt	-12.2 Mt	-35.8 Mt	
Category C - Approaches Reflecting neither Responsibility nor Capability								
not considered	2016	66 %	84 %	108 %	66 %	84 %	108 %	none
		24.3 Mt	11.6 Mt	-5.6 Mt	24.2 Mt	11.4 Mt	-5.7 Mt	

Table A-3: Detailed results (in terms of percentage reduction as well as emissions allocations in MtCO₂eq; exclusive of LULUCF) for the same approaches as in table 4 for a global mitigation effort consistent with limiting warming to 1.5 °C with 67 % probability.

Progressivity Approach	Emissions Responsibility Start Date	Reductions in % below 1990 by and Allocation in Mt CO ₂ eq in (before adjustment)			Reductions in % below 1990 by and Allocation in Mt CO ₂ eq in (with adjustment)			Equity Principles
		2030	2035	2045	2030	2035	2045	
		Category A - Approaches Reflecting Both Responsibility and Capability						
High Progressivity	1850	143 %	197 %	271 %	152 %	206 %	281 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-30.9 Mt	-69.5 Mt	-123.2 Mt	-37.7 Mt	-76.3 Mt	-130.0 Mt	
	1950	143 %	197 %	272 %	153 %	206 %	281 %	
		-31.1 Mt	-69.8 Mt	-123.4 Mt	-37.9 Mt	-76.6 Mt	-130.2 Mt	Responsibility, Capability, Need
	1990	139 %	191 %	262 %	148 %	200 %	271 %	
		-28.2 Mt	-65.5 Mt	-116.8 Mt	-34.7 Mt	-72.0 Mt	-123.3 Mt	
Medium Progressivity	1850	154 %	210 %	291 %	166 %	221 %	302 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-39.0 Mt	-79.3 Mt	-137.2 Mt	-47.1 Mt	-87.4 Mt	-145.3 Mt	
	1950	155 %	211 %	291 %	166 %	222 %	303 %	
		-39.5 Mt	-79.8 Mt	-137.6 Mt	-47.6 Mt	-87.9 Mt	-145.8 Mt	Responsibility, Capability, Need
	1990	146 %	197 %	270 %	156 %	208 %	281 %	
		-32.8 Mt	-70.1 Mt	-122.5 Mt	-40.2 Mt	-77.5 Mt	-129.9 Mt	
Category B - Approaches Reflecting either Responsibility or Capability but not both								
High Progr.	2016	132 %	177 %	244 %	140 %	186 %	252 %	Capability, Need
		-22.9 Mt	-55.8 Mt	-103.5 Mt	-28.9 Mt	-61.8 Mt	-109.5 Mt	
Medium Progr.	2016	132 %	176 %	241 %	141 %	185 %	249 %	Capability, Need
		-23.1 Mt	-55.0 Mt	-101.1 Mt	-29.4 Mt	-61.4 Mt	-107.5 Mt	
High Progr.	responsibility not considered	203 %	290 %	431 %	219 %	306 %	447 %	Capability, Need
		-74.3 Mt	-136.6 Mt	-238.3 Mt	-85.9 Mt	-148.2 Mt	-249.9 Mt	
Medium Progr.		211 %	295 %	430 %	228 %	313 %	448 %	Capability, Need
		-79.6 Mt	-140.6 Mt	-237.4 Mt	-92.3 Mt	-153.4 Mt	-250.1 Mt	
capacity not considered	1850	108 %	143 %	193 %	114 %	149 %	198 %	Responsibility
		-5.9 Mt	-30.7 Mt	-66.6 Mt	-10.1 Mt	-35.0 Mt	-70.9 Mt	
	1950	109 %	144 %	193 %	115 %	150 %	199 %	
		-6.6 Mt	-31.5 Mt	-67.1 Mt	-11.0 Mt	-35.9 Mt	-71.5 Mt	Responsibility
	1990	84 %	109 %	146 %	87 %	112 %	149 %	
		11.2 Mt	-6.7 Mt	-33.0 Mt	9.1 Mt	-8.8 Mt	-35.2 Mt	
Category C - Approaches Reflecting neither Responsibility nor Capability								
not considered	2016	64 %	81 %	107 %	64 %	81 %	108 %	none
		26.1 Mt	13.8 Mt	-5.4 Mt	25.9 Mt	13.5 Mt	-5.6 Mt	

Table A-4: A version of table A

Progressivity Approach	Emissions Responsibility Start Date	Reductions in % below 1990 by and Allocation in Mt CO ₂ eq in (before adjustment)			Reductions in % below 1990 by and Allocation in Mt CO ₂ eq in (with adjustment)			Equity Principles
		2030	2035	2045	2030	2035	2045	
		Category A - Approaches Reflecting Both Responsibility and Capability						
High Progressivity	1850	149 %	204 %	270 %	158 %	213 %	280 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-35.3 Mt	-75.0 Mt	-122.6 Mt	-41.9 Mt	-81.6 Mt	-129.2 Mt	
	1950	149 %	205 %	271 %	159 %	214 %	280 %	
		-35.5 Mt	-75.3 Mt	-122.8 Mt	-42.1 Mt	-81.9 Mt	-129.4 Mt	Responsibility, Capability, Need
	1990	145 %	198 %	262 %	154 %	207 %	270 %	
		-32.5 Mt	-70.8 Mt	-116.2 Mt	-38.8 Mt	-77.0 Mt	-122.5 Mt	
Medium Progressivity	1850	161 %	218 %	290 %	172 %	229 %	301 %	Responsibility, Capability, Need
		-43.9 Mt	-85.2 Mt	-136.9 Mt	-51.7 Mt	-93.1 Mt	-144.7 Mt	
	1950	162 %	219 %	291 %	173 %	230 %	302 %	
		-44.4 Mt	-85.8 Mt	-137.3 Mt	-52.3 Mt	-93.7 Mt	-145.2 Mt	Responsibility, Capability, Need
	1990	152 %	205 %	270 %	162 %	215 %	280 %	
		-37.4 Mt	-75.6 Mt	-122.1 Mt	-44.5 Mt	-82.8 Mt	-129.2 Mt	
Category B - Approaches Reflecting either Responsibility or Capability but not both								
High Progr.	2016	137 %	184 %	243 %	146 %	192 %	251 %	Capability, Need
		-27.0 Mt	-60.5 Mt	-103.2 Mt	-32.8 Mt	-66.3 Mt	-109.0 Mt	
Medium Progr.	2016	138 %	183 %	240 %	146 %	192 %	249 %	Capability, Need
		-27.2 Mt	-59.8 Mt	-100.9 Mt	-33.3 Mt	-66.0 Mt	-107.0 Mt	
High Progr.	responsibility not considered	212 %	302 %	432 %	228 %	317 %	447 %	Capability, Need
		-80.7 Mt	-145.0 Mt	-238.8 Mt	-91.9 Mt	-156.3 Mt	-250.0 Mt	
Medium Progr.		221 %	309 %	432 %	238 %	326 %	449 %	Capability, Need
		-86.9 Mt	-150.1 Mt	-239.0 Mt	-99.3 Mt	-162.5 Mt	-251.3 Mt	
capacity not considered	1850	108 %	143 %	185 %	113 %	147 %	189 %	Responsibility
		-5.6 Mt	-30.6 Mt	-60.8 Mt	-9.0 Mt	-34.0 Mt	-64.3 Mt	
	1950	115 %	151 %	195 %	120 %	156 %	201 %	
		-10.5 Mt	-36.4 Mt	-68.3 Mt	-14.7 Mt	-40.6 Mt	-72.5 Mt	Responsibility
	1990	88 %	114 %	147 %	91 %	117 %	150 %	
		8.5 Mt	-10.1 Mt	-33.7 Mt	6.4 Mt	-12.2 Mt	-35.8 Mt	
Category C - Approaches Reflecting neither Responsibility nor Capability								
not considered	2016	66 %	84 %	108 %	66 %	84 %	108 %	none
		24.3 Mt	11.6 Mt	-5.6 Mt	24.2 Mt	11.4 Mt	-5.7 Mt	

Table A-3 for the C1₈₃ subset of mitigation scenarios.

Progressivity Approach	Emissions Responsibility Start Date	Reductions in % below 1990 by (before adjustment)								
		2030			2035			2045		
		all GHGs	CO ₂ only	non-CO ₂	all GHGs	CO ₂ only	non-CO ₂	all GHGs	CO ₂ only	non-CO ₂
Category A - Approaches Reflecting Both Responsibility and Capability										
High Progressivity	1850	149%	154%	129%	204%	211%	177%	270%	287%	207%
	1950	149%	155%	129%	205%	212%	177%	271%	287%	207%
	1990	145%	150%	128%	198%	204%	175%	262%	276%	204%
Medium Progressivity	1850	161%	168%	133%	218%	228%	181%	290%	311%	209%
	1950	162%	169%	134%	219%	229%	182%	291%	311%	210%
	1990	152%	157%	131%	205%	212%	178%	270%	286%	206%

Table A-5: Breakdown of reduction percentages (relative to 1990 levels; before adjustment) in non-CO₂ and CO₂ portions (both excluding LULUCF) of the Category A approaches from table 4 in the main text.

Appendix 2: Methodological Transparency

Any study design requires many decisions and assumptions to be made by researchers and often, those remain unreported. Transparency of methodological decision making is particularly important for studies investigating explicitly normative subject matter, such as the present one (Dooley et al. 2021). While many of the normative decisions and assumptions (and, where applicable, their justifications) are detailed in the “Request from Aurora” and the main text, the author also made additional decisions and assumptions while carrying out the work, many of which have normative content – in the choice itself and/or in the impact of the choice on the results – and can therefore not, in good faith, be considered neutral choices.

This appendix is the result of a good faith attempt by the author to document those additional choices and to explain, where applicable, the rationale and the potential impact on results (in direction and/or order of magnitude). Calling it an “attempt” reflects the author’s humility in the context of an acknowledgment that many of such choices are made reflexively or unconsciously, and as such, any such catalogue will inevitably be incomplete despite best efforts. For each of the items, it is also specified whether the choice is primarily based on common practice in the literature, the author’s expert judgement, the “Request from Aurora,” or a combination of these factors.

Overarching

- Deciding the threshold level of incomes for inequality-aware approaches to accounting for capacity
 - *Common Practice / Author’s Expert Judgement.* Studies utilizing the Climate Equity Reference Framework typically use an income threshold of \$7,500 per person per year, or approximately \$20 per person per day, as a threshold income (both values in 2005 PPP USD). This is slightly higher than a global poverty line of about \$16 per day (PPP adjusted to 2005 USD), which, in turn represents the income levels where the typical manifestations of poverty (low educational attainment, high relative food expenditures, malnutrition, high infant mortality, shelter precarity, etc.) begin to be overcome, according to empirical analysis (Pritchett 2003, 2006). According to Pritchett this is “the level of income at which people typically achieve acceptable levels of the Millennium Development Goal indicators (such as universal primary school completion)” (Pritchett 2006: 13) which “is justifiable, more consistent with international fairness, and is a better foundation for [...] poverty reduction” (Pritchett 2003: 3). The present analysis is utilizing this income threshold for the “inequality-aware capacity adjusted” approaches for budget and pathway allocations as well as for the lower income threshold for the effort sharing allocations of the Climate Equity Reference framework. To make the 2005 PPP value consistent with the data sources used for Gini coefficients and GDP, compound inflation between 2005 and 2025 was applied to the \$7,500 value and an inflation-adjusted value of \$12,500 was used to represent the same threshold level.
- Deciding the time horizon for considering past emissions
 - *Aurora Request / Common Practice.* Aurora Request specified that the notion of historical responsibility should consider emissions at least as far back as 1990. Other common dates in the literature are 1950 and 1850, for reasons explained in the main text, and have also been used.

- Deciding which allocation approaches to include and exclude in the quantification exercise
 - *Aurora Request / Common Practice / Author's Expert Judgement.* The Request from Aurora articulated a primary interest in allocation approaches that consider both capacity and responsibility, and provided further detail with regards to defining responsibility. As such, the selection of approaches for inclusion in the quantified results was focussed on “Category A” approaches. Additional approaches were selected based on the author’s judgement of the common practice in the literature and of the author’s judgement which specific approach would serve as a suitable representative of a broader class of approaches. Approaches that have not been commonly used in the literature in recent years were generally excluded (e.g., Meyer 1999; Winkler et al. 2011).
- Choices of data sources
 - *Common Practice / Author's Expert Judgement.*
 - Most data sources match those used for the Fair Shares python package, namely the IPCC AR6 scenario database (Byers et al. 2022) with updates from Gidden et al. (Gidden et al. 2023a, 2023b) for mitigation scenario data, IPCC AR6 as updated by Forster et al. (2025) for RCB data, PRIMAP-hist (Gütschow et al. 2025) for historical emissions data, IMF World Economic Outlook for GDP data (IMF 2025), and United Nations’ World Population Prospects for population data (United Nations 2024). This set of input data sources is also used, for example, in the effort sharing calculations of the European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change (ESABCC 2023) and individual data sources of this set are commonly used in the effort sharing literature.
 - For Gini coefficients, the World Inequality Database (WID.world 2025) was used instead of the World Income Inequality Database (UNU-WIDER 2025) since it provides a more complete time series for the countries in the database. The impact on fair shares allocations of the difference between the two data sources is discussed elsewhere (Holz et al. 2024), and generally leads to larger allocations for wealthier countries.
- Territorial emissions accounting (ignore emissions embedded in trade)
 - *Common Practice / Aurora Request.* Owing to the use of territorial emissions accounting in the UNFCCC and in most national climate legislation, it is the approach most commonly used in the effort sharing literature. Alternatively, consumption-based accounting would also consider the emissions embedded in goods and services consumed in a country (but produced elsewhere) and generally tends to lead to more stringent allocations for most developed countries. Aurora’s request specified that in order to facilitate comparison between Sweden’s fair share and its mitigation targets, the report should focus on territorial emissions.
- Slope for extrapolation of recent historical emissions for 2024 and 2025 for Sweden
 - *Author's expert judgement.* Since 2023 is the most recent year with data in current historical emissions data sets with global coverage, emissions for each country were linearly extrapolated to 2024 and 2025 using the average annual change of the five-year period from 2019-2023. In the author’s judgement this extrapolation reflects Sweden’s

general emissions trend since 2000, even though it leads to a slight underestimation of Sweden's shortfall (Naturvardsverket 2025; SCB 2025).

- Decision to categorize specific approaches as Category A, B, and C.
 - *Aurora Request / Author's Expert Judgement*. The Author assigned specific allocation approaches to the A, B, and C categories of the Request from Aurora based on the author's understanding of the Request.

Specific to calculating allocations of remaining carbon budgets

- Adjusting RCBs for bunkers and LULUCF, specifically the choice to adjust the RCBs so that the amount left for budget sharing among nations does not include emissions from LULUCF and international aviation and shipping (bunker fuels); as well as the assumption of the level of LULUCF and bunker fuel emissions up to the date at which the RCB would be exhausted.
 - *Common Practice*. It is very common in the literature to exclude LULUCF and bunker emissions in effort sharing calculations.
 - *Author's Expert Judgement*. The level of assumed future LULUCF and bunker emissions is based on the assumption that the levels of these emissions would remain constant at the level of recent years until the date that the RCB would be exhausted at current rate of depletion (Forster et al. 2025).
Specifically, Forster et al. give RCBs as of 2025 of 80 GtCO₂ (RCB₆₇) and 30 GtCO₂ (RCB₈₃), respectively, and estimated CO₂ emissions in 2024 as 42.4 GtCO₂, implying an exhaustion year of 2025 for RCB₈₃ and 2026 for RCB₆₇. Bunker emissions are given in the same study as 1.2 GtCO₂ and LULUCF as 4.2 GtCO₂ in 2024. Assuming, for simplicity, these values to remain constant over the next two years results in a total adjustment of 5.4 GtCO₂ for RCB₈₃ and 10.8 GtCO₂ for RCB₆₇ for the period between 2025 to the depletion year.

Specific to calculating allocations in the context of mitigation pathways

- Selecting a single pathway from the scenarios ensemble of the IPCC AR6 scenario database as representative for each probability of temperature outcome, specifically, choosing the “median” pathway relative to the full range of pathways that correspond to the given temperature outcome.
 - *Common Practice*. This approach is commonly used in the literature (e.g., Rajamani et al. 2021; UNEP 2019)
- Considering sub-sets of the category C1 pathways of the IPCC's AR6 WG3 scenario set
 - *Aurora Request*. To align with Aurora's legal argumentation, Aurora requested to restrict analysis to pathways that limit warming to 1.5°C with at least 67% and 83% probability, respectively.
- No further filtering of scenario pathways. Alternatively, pathways could have further been screened based, for example, on their assumptions about future level of CDR, length and magnitude of overshoot, and near-term mitigation stringency. Such screening is sometimes applied in the literature (e.g., CAT 2023) to reflect authors' assessment about the plausibility and sustainability of certain model assumptions and their differentiated impacts across geographies, time, and socio-economic dimensions such as income/wealth, gender, race.
 - *Common Practice / Author's Expert Judgement*. Applying additional filters is not very common in the literature and was therefore not judged necessary for the present report

(i.e. the common practice of not filtering is followed here). Adding such filters would be expected to increase the near-term stringency of mitigation.

- Decision to allocate net emissions, choice to use same allocation approach for CO₂ and non-CO₂
 - *Common Practice*. Generally, allocation studies do not differentiate between the allocation of gross positive and gross negative emissions, or between the allocation of CO₂ and non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions, despite ethical (e.g. food vs. energy) and methodological/physical (timing of emissions, impact on atmospheric accumulation) differences. Recently, studies have begun to explore differentiated allocations for gross positive emissions on one hand and carbon dioxide removal on the other hand (CVF 2022; Robiou Du Pont et al. 2025), but this has not yet become common practice.
- Decision to account for near recent shortfall of actual emission relative to allocations; decisions regarding how to account for the shortfall (e.g. across which time horizon to account for it)
 - *Aurora Request / Author's expert judgement*. The question of how to account for excess emissions relative to equitable allocations where allocations have been allocated in the recent past (e.g. in 2016, as per Aurora's request) implies important normative considerations. Recent work has increasingly highlighted that the tendency of an earlier generation of allocation studies to favour "continuous" allocations from current emissions levels introduces a "grandfathering" bias that structurally favours historically higher emitting countries (Robiou Du Pont et al. 2025). Adjusting future allocations for excess emission of the recent past is an emerging practice to address this bias (Holz 2024a) and has been explicitly requested by Aurora, including that the time horizon of the adjustment is "the period until 2045."
- Decision to disregard approaches with transition periods
 - *Author's expert judgement*. It has been pointed out that "transition periods" where allocation transitions from present emissions levels over time to an equity-based allocation introduce a "grandfathering bias" and allocate the majority of the remaining carbon budget based on "grandfathering" thus resulting in a structural bias toward historically high emitting and higher-capacity countries (Dooley et al. 2021; Kartha, Athanasiou, et al. 2018; Robiou Du Pont et al. 2025). To avoid this issue, allocation approaches with transition periods have been disregarded for the present study and all allocation is immediately based on the relevant equity principle.
- CERf: choice of baseline projection algorithm
 - *Common practice / Author's expert judgement*: Allocations using the Climate Equity Reference framework depend on a baseline projection to calculate allocations of mitigation effort. The baseline projection approach used here follows the standard approach used by the Climate Equity Reference Calculator (Holz et al. 2024; Kemp-Benedict et al. 2018).
- Choices of specific parameters for both Fair Shares python package and Climate Equity Reference Calculator.
 - *Common practice / Author's expert judgement*. For both software tools utilized in the study, several methodological choices had to be made to parameterize each tool that were not discussed as normative choices in the main text, even though they have an impact on the results. For the Fair Shares python package, specifically, these choices are,

for capacity based allocations, the functional form of the adjustment (inverse hyperbolic sine or inverse power function, where the latter was chosen because it allows for larger impacts of the independent variable on allocations), the exponent for the inverse power function (1 was chosen to limit excessive impact of extreme values), the maximum deviation (again limiting the impact of extreme values; no limit was implemented), and for inequality-aware approaches additionally the income floor (\$12,500) and the limit to the strength of the inequality-aware adjustment (limiting to 50% of maximum adjustment). These choices mostly matched those used in other studies using the tool (ESABCC 2023; Pelz et al. 2023), with the exception of the income floor, which was selected to match that selected for the quantifications using the Climate Equity Reference Calculator.

For the Climate Equity Reference Calculator, parameterizations were chosen to match those commonly used by studies utilizing the Calculator (Civil Society Equity Review 2015, 2025; Holz et al. 2018). Specifically, the “Medium Progressivity” parameterization utilizes a lower threshold of USD \$12,500 (adjusted for purchasing power parity), which is the inflation adjusted figure of the USD \$7,500 value used by the Civil Society Equity Review. Incomes of individuals below this threshold are exempted from being considered capability of the country under this parameterization and the emissions associated with consumption below this threshold are exempted from being considered responsibility. All incomes and emissions above this threshold are fully considered capability or responsibility of the country, respectively. See “Overarching” in Appendix 2 above for empirical justifications of this income level. For the “High Progressivity” parameterization, a further higher threshold is introduced with incomes and emissions between the thresholds linearly increasing from 0% to 100% in terms of how much they count towards the country’s capability and responsibility, respectively. In other words, only very small fractions of incomes and emissions just above the lower threshold are considered, whereas all income and all emissions above the higher threshold are considered. This mimics the income tax regimes in most countries, where above an exemption threshold the marginal tax rate gradually increases up to a maximum rate. Again, here, an inflation-adjusted value is used, i.e. USD \$85,000 instead of the non-adjusted \$50,000 used by the Civil Society Equity Review.